

1 Glycosaminoglycans from marine sources as therapeutic 2 agents

3
4 *Jesus Valcarcel^{a,b}, *José Antonio Vázquez^b, Ramón Novoa-Carballal^{c,d},
5 Ricardo Pérez-Martín^a & Rui L. Reis^{c,d}

6
7 ^aGroup of Food Biochemistry, Marine Research Institute (IIM-CSIC), R/
8 Eduardo Cabello, 6, CP 36208, Vigo (Pontevedra), Spain.

9
10 ^bGroup of Recycling and Valorisation of Waste Materials (REVAL), Marine
11 Research Institute (IIM-CSIC), R/ Eduardo Cabello, 6, CP 36208, Vigo
12 (Pontevedra), Spain.

13
14 ^c3B's Research Group – Biomaterials, Biodegradables and Biomimetics,
15 University of Minho, Headquarters of the European Institute of Excellence on
16 Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine, AvePark, 4805-017 Barco,
17 Guimarães, Portugal.

18
19 ^dICVS/3B's - PT Government Associate Laboratory, Braga/Guimarães,
20 Portugal.

21
22 *Corresponding authors

23
24 Keywords: glycosaminoglycans; marine, therapeutic; regenerative medicine;
25 tissue engineering; nervous system; cancer; antiviral; anticoagulant;
26 inflammation.

27 **Abstract**

28 Glycosaminoglycans (GAGs) in marine animals are different to those of
29 terrestrial organisms, mainly in terms of molecular weight and sulfation. The
30 therapeutic properties of GAGs are related to their ability to interact with
31 proteins, which is very much influenced by sulfation position and patterns. Since
32 currently CS cannot be chemically synthesized, it is sourced from natural
33 products, with high intra- but also inter-species variability, in terms of chain
34 length, disaccharide composition and sulfation pattern. Consequently, sulfated
35 GAGs are the most interesting molecules in the marine environment and
36 constitute the focus of the present review. In particular, chondroitin sulfate (CS)
37 appears as the most promising compound. CS-E chains extracted from squid
38 posses antiviral and anti-metastatic activities and seem to impart signalling
39 properties and improve the mechanical performance of cartilage engineering
40 constructs; Squid CS-E and octopus CS-K, DS (dermatan sulfate) from sea
41 squirts (-K units) and sea urchins (-E units) and hybrids CS/DS from sharks (-B,
42 -D and -E units) promote neurite outgrowth and could be valuable materials for
43 nerve regeneration. Also displaying antiviral and anti-metastatic properties, a
44 rare CS with fucosylated branches isolated from sea cucumbers is an
45 anticoagulant and anti-inflammatory agent. In this same line, marine heparin
46 extracted from shrimp and sea squirt has proven anti-inflammatory properties,
47 with the added advantage of decreased risk of bleeding because of its low
48 anticoagulant activity.
49
50

1. Introduction

Glycosaminoglycans (GAGs) are linear polysaccharides ubiquitous in the extracellular matrix (ECM) of most animal tissues, either free or bound to proteins. Once thought mere filling material, GAGs are currently recognized to be involved in a number of functions fundamental for cellular communication, differentiation and growth. Therefore, it is reasonable to conceive these molecules as potential therapeutic agents, some already realized as is the case with heparin, which has been the anticoagulant of choice for decades. Probably the most extensively investigated GAG, new roles of heparin are still presently emerging, which serves to illustrate the potential that GAGs hold.

From the chemical point of view, GAGs are polymers consisting of repeating O-linked disaccharide units. These units are formed by an aminosugar and a sugar acid (uronic acid), except keratan sulphate (KS) which has β -D-galactose (Gal) instead of the sugar acid, linked to N-acetyl α -D-glucosamine (GlcNAc) by alternating β 1,4 and β 1,3 glycosidic bonds. The amino sugar is sometimes acetylated and the sugar acid can either be glucuronic acid (GlcA) or its isomer iduronic acid (IdoA) (Figure 1). GAG chains are in most cases sulfated, except hyaluronan (HA). Sulfation in KS occurs exclusively at position 6 of the galactose and acetylglucosamine rings, whereas other sulphated GAGs display greater diversity in the position of sulphate groups. This diversity is further increased by the epimerization of the uronic acid, leading to a number of disaccharides, in part responsible for the considerable complexity in GAG chains. Both chondroitin sulphate (CS) and dermatan sulphate (DS) contain the same aminosugar (N-acetyl α -D-galactosamine, GalNAc), but glucuronic acid in CS undergoes epimerization to iduronic acid in DS. Sulfation at different positions and in different grades produce mirror disaccharide type units in both CS and DS (Figure 2).

(FIGURE 1)

(FIGURE 2)

Both heparin (HEP)/heparan sulphate (HS) and CS share the first biosynthetic step, but with the subsequent addition of N-acetyl to glucosamine (GluNAc) in the first case, instead of GalNAc. This initial disaccharide is later modified by sulfation of the aminosugar, leading to sulfoglucosamine, and epimerization of the iduronic acid. Further sulfation occurs in both the uronic acid and sulfoglucosamine, producing the most negatively charged polymer known in nature (Figure 3). The degree and type of enzymatic modifications after polymerization lead to structural differences between HS and HEP, the latter being more extensively modified (Sugahara and Kitagawa, 2002). These differences between both polymers are mainly in terms of degree of sulfation and epimerization of the uronic ring. In HEP, the most abundant disaccharide is formed by iduronic acid and N-sulfo- α -D-glucosamine sulphated in positions 2 and 6 respectively, while in HS it is the unsulfated GlcA-(1 \rightarrow 4)-GlcNAc. Furthermore, HS chains are segregated into unsulfated and highly sulphated heparin-like domains, producing a fine structure which influences HS interactions with protein ligands (Li and Kusche-Gullberg, 2016; Rabenstein, 2002). In animal tissues, HS is expressed and excreted by most mammalian cells and is widely distributed as proteoglycans in the ECM and at the cell

1 surface. On the other hand, HEP is only expressed in mast cells of connective
2 tissue and stored in free form, non-covalently bound to basic proteases, in
3 cytoplasmatic secretory granules (Rabenstein, 2002).

4
5 **(FIGURE 3)**

6
7 GAGs can be followed throughout animal evolution, starting from primitive
8 sponges, containing no GAGs, to humans. Along the way, some structures are
9 widely distributed, while others are absent in lower organisms or exist with
10 limited complexity (Yamada et al., 2011). This diversity also reflects in the
11 different evolutionary

12
13 pathways of marine and terrestrial animals, which have led to rare and
14 sometimes unique GAGs in marine organisms. Not surprisingly, considerable
15 effort has been placed in investigating their therapeutic properties and potential
16 uses.

17
18 The therapeutic possibilities of GAGs are based on their effects on coagulation,
19 thrombosis, inflammation, cancer, viral infection and tissue development. In
20 some cases as a safer alternative to established applications, such as the
21 anticoagulant heparin, but also with potential in tissue regeneration and in the
22 development of antiviral and anti-tumour drugs.

23
24 The bioactivity and therapeutic properties of GAGs depend on their ability to
25 bind to proteins, which is to a great extent influenced by sulfation (Gulati and
26 Poluri, 2016; Hileman et al., 1998; Soares da Costa et al., 2017). Consequently,
27 the main interest of marine GAGs resides on peculiarities related in most cases
28 to distinct sulfation with different interrelated aspects. First, the relative
29 abundance of sulfated units varies in marine and terrestrial GAGs (Table 1)
30 producing changes in charge density among GAG chains. Second, rare
31 disaccharide units, such as CS K, are only found in marine animals, (Higashi et
32 al., 2015a; Sugahara et al., 1996). Finally, some marine GAGs show unusual
33 patterns (Chavante et al., 2014), specific sequences of consecutive
34 saccharides. Particular patterns are known to be required for the binding of
35 heparin to antithrombin (Petitou et al., 2003) and fibroblast growth factor
36 (Capila and Linhardt, 2002), and of HS to the herpes simplex virus (Liu et al.,
37 2002; Shukla et al., 1999). However, in most cases interactions between GAGs
38 and proteins are not so specific and seem to be rather influenced by charge
39 density and the presence of particular sulfated units (Li and Kusche-Gullberg,
40 2016; Yamada and Sugahara, 2008).

41
42 In both situations, marine sulfated GAGs add new possibilities to current
43 terrestrial sources and they will constitute the focus of the present review,
44 incorporating recent studies using CS/DS and HEP/HS extracted exclusively
45 from marine animals. KS, also sulphated, is found in shark cartilage (Zhang et
46 al., 2005), zebra fish (Souza et al., 2007) and the skin of other teleost fish (Ito et
47 al., 1984; Ralphs and Benjamin, 1992), but to the best of our knowledge, the
48 therapeutic properties of marine KS have not been explored. Finally, hyaluronan
49 can be isolated from the eyes of fish (Murado et al., 2012). However, marine
50 hyaluronan is not of particular interest since, lacking sulphate groups, it is only

1 defined by its molecular weight. Furthermore, it is at present mainly produced
 2 by bacteria from the *Streptococcus zooepidemicus* species (Amado et al., 2016;
 3 Vázquez et al., 2009; Vázquez et al., 2010; Vázquez et al., 2015), making its
 4 extraction from marine organisms uneconomic.

5
 6 Other polysaccharides from marine origin also show potential as therapeutic
 7 agents, including those produced by eukaryotes (alginate, fucoidans, ulvans,
 8 carrageenans, chitosan) and prokaryotes (exopolysaccharides and extracellular
 9 polymeric substances). However, these compounds lay beyond the scope of the
 10 present work and are reviewed elsewhere (Cardoso et al., 2016; Delbarre-
 11 Ladrat et al., 2014; Senni et al., 2011; Silva et al., 2012).

12 13 **2. Regenerative medicine**

14 GAGs play a pivotal role in the development of new tissue in animals and as a
 15 consequence, tissue regeneration strategies have in many cases incorporated
 16 GAGs. Regardless of the strategy chosen, it is fundamental to provide an
 17 environment with the right properties to allow and spatially direct the growth of
 18 cells. GAGs are particularly suited to this purpose through their ability to bind to
 19 proteins forming proteoglycans and sequester growth factors, which are central
 20 in the control of cell differentiation and function (Place et al., 2009).

21
 22 The involvement of CS and DS in the repair mechanisms of the central nervous
 23 system, liver development and connective tissue repair have spurred interest
 24 about potential uses in regenerative medicine. It is apparent that the sulfation
 25 pattern of specific sequences within CS and DS chains are key to the
 26 interaction with bioactive proteins related to the proliferation of neural stem cells
 27 and hepatocells (Shuhei and Kazuyuki, 2008). Since currently CS cannot be
 28 chemically synthesized, it is sourced from natural products, with high intra- but
 29 also inter-species variability, in terms of chain length, disaccharide composition
 30 and sulfation pattern (Martel-Pelletier et al., 2015).

31
 32 The variability in CS composition extends to its origin, making it possible to
 33 differentiate between CS from terrestrial and marine sources (Thomas et al.,
 34 2011; Zang et al., 2012). One way to look at this difference is in terms of the
 35 proportion of disaccharide units: CS from terrestrial animals is almost
 36 exclusively composed of non-sulfated (O) and monosulfated (A and C) units,
 37 while in marine species the proportion of disulfated (D, E and B) units is higher
 38 (Table 1). Furthermore, marine GAG chains tend to be longer (Table 2), with the
 39 largest differences found in CS.

40 41 **2.1. Cartilage regeneration**

42 The objective of cartilage engineering strategies is the development of a
 43 scaffold material capable of supporting the compression forces applied to the
 44 joint while creating the right conditions for implanted cells to produce new
 45

GAG	Source	% of disaccharide units							Ref
		non-sulfated	monosulfated		disulfated				
		O	A	C	D	B	E	K	
CS	Shark cartilage	2-5	28-30	37-50	15-23	1-2	2-4	-	(Maccari and Volpi, 2003; Mucci et al., 2000; Volpi, 2000, 2004, 2007)

CS	Small-spotted catshark (<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>) fin	22	31	32	16	-	-	-	(Novoa-Carballal et al., 2017)
CS	Small-spotted catshark (<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>) head	14	36	29	18	-	-	-	(Novoa-Carballal et al., 2017)
CS	Small-spotted catshark (<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>) skeleton	15	39	30	17	-	-	-	(Novoa-Carballal et al., 2017)
CS/DS	Shortfin mako shark (<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>) dried fins (without skin and cartilage)	3	40	25	9	17	5	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS/DS	Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>) dried fins (without skin and cartilage)	16	46	20	4	10	3	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS/DS	Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>) raw fins (without skin)	1	25	52	18	-	3	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS	Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>) head	16	10	64	9	-	-	-	(Novoa-Carballal et al., 2017)
CS/DS	Cloudy catshark (<i>Scyliorhinus torazame</i>) whole fins	10	24	45	15	4	3	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS/DS	Birdbeak dogfish (<i>Deania calcea</i>) whole fins	20	16	55	6	3	-	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS/DS	Smalltooth sand tiger (<i>Odontaspis ferox</i>) whole fins	4	23	57	14	1	1	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS/DS	Kitefin shark (<i>Dalatias licha</i>) whole fins	6	24	56	8	4	2	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS/DS	Friiled shark (<i>Clamydoselachus anguineus</i>) whole fins	40	16	37	2	4	1	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS/DS	Goblin shark (<i>Mitsukurina owstoni</i>) whole fins	11	15	67	5	2	1	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS/DS	Spotless smooth-hound (<i>Mustelus griseus</i>) whole fins	7	32	35	20	3	3	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS/DS	Silver Chimaera (<i>Chimaera phantasma</i>) whole fins	6	27	41	18	3	3	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS/DS	Red stingray (<i>Dasyatis akajei</i>) whole fin	4	31	44	19	2	1	-	(Higashi et al., 2015b)
CS	Skate cartilage	3	43	39	13	1	1	-	(Volpi, 2007)
CS	Thornback skate (<i>Raja clavata</i>) skeleton	19	16	56	9	-	-	-	(Novoa-Carballal et al., 2017)
CS	Monkfish bones	13	51	28	1	1	6	-	(Maccari et al., 2015)
CS	Codfish bones	3	60	27	10	-	-	-	(Maccari et al., 2015)
CS	Spiny dogfish bones	7	25	56	11	-	1	-	(Maccari et al., 2015)
CS	Salmon bones	8	51	37	4	-	-	-	(Maccari et al., 2015)
CS	Tuna bones	2	63	28	5	1	1	-	(Maccari et al., 2015)
CS	Sturgeon bone	7	38	55	-	-	-	-	(Maccari et al., 2010)
CS	Diamond squid (<i>Thysanoteuthis rhombus</i>) fin	77	8	4	-	-	11	-	(Tamura et al., 2009)
CS	Diamond squid (<i>Thysanoteuthis rhombus</i>) arms	88	6	2	-	-	4	-	(Tamura et al., 2009)
CS	Diamond squid (<i>Thysanoteuthis rhombus</i>) skin	17	26	19	-	-	38	-	(Tamura et al., 2009)
CS	Diamond squid (<i>Thysanoteuthis rhombus</i>) head	33	31	15	-	-	21	-	(Tamura et al., 2009)
CS	Diamond squid (<i>Thysanoteuthis rhombus</i>) eyes	13	52	13	-	-	22	-	(Tamura et al., 2009)
CS	Diamond squid (<i>Thysanoteuthis rhombus</i>) mantle	4	54	16	-	-	26	-	(Tamura et al., 2009)

CS	Octopus (<i>Enteroctopus dofleini</i>) cartilage	5	77	-	-	-	4	14	(Higashi et al., 2015a)
DS	<i>Halocynthia pyriformis</i> (Ascidian)	-	29	1			70	-	(Pavao et al., 1998)
DS	<i>Styela plicata</i> (Ascidian)	-	28	1	5	66	-	-	(Pavao et al., 1998)
Terrestrial									
DS	Bovine lung	15	63	9	1	12	-	-	(Volpi, 1999)
CS	Bovine lung	3	41	54	2	-	-	-	(Volpi, 1999)
DS	Bovine heart	4	61	19	2	13	-	-	(Volpi, 1999)
CS	Bovine trachea	6-10	51-61	33-41	0-1	-	-	-	(Maccari and Volpi, 2003; Mucci et al., 2000; Volpi, 2000, 2004, 2007)
CS	Porcine trachea	3-6	66-82	15-26	0-2	-	-	-	(Maccari and Volpi, 2003; Mucci et al., 2000; Volpi, 2000, 2004)
CS	Porcine nose cartilage	6	80	14	-	-	-	-	(Volpi, 2007)
DS	Porcine skin	-	84	3	-	3	9	-	(Volpi, 2004)
DS	Pig mucosa	2	75	9	-	5	8	-	(Volpi, 2000)
CS	Chicken trachea	8-13	69-72	18-20	-	-	-	-	(Maccari and Volpi, 2003; Volpi, 2004, 2007)

Table 1. Disaccharide composition of chondroitin sulphate (CS), dermatan sulfate (DS) and hybrid chains (CS/DS) isolated from terrestrial and marine animals.

GAG	Source	Mw (kDa)	Ref
Marine			
CS	Shark cartilage	20 to >50	(Maccari and Volpi, 2003; Mucci et al., 2000; Volpi, 2000, 2004, 2007)
CS	Small-spotted catshark (<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>) fin	43-45	(Novoa-Carballal et al., 2017)
CS	Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>) head	60	(Novoa-Carballal et al., 2017)
CS	Skate cartilage	27-34	(Volpi, 2007)
CS	Thornback skate (<i>Raja clavata</i>) skeleton	44	(Novoa-Carballal et al., 2017)
CS	Monkfish bones	49	(Maccari et al., 2015)
CS	Codfish bones	18	(Maccari et al., 2015)
CS	Spiny dogfish bones	13	(Maccari et al., 2015)
CS	Salmon bones	20	(Maccari et al., 2015)
CS	Tuna bones	33	(Maccari et al., 2015)
CS	Sturgeon bone	37	(Maccari et al., 2010)
Chondroitin sulfate (CS) & dermatan sulfate (DS)	CS	Octopus (<i>Enteroctopus dofleini</i>) cartilage	67 (Higashi et al., 2015a)
	DS	Ray (<i>Raja radula</i>) skin	31 (Mansour et al., 2009)
	CS/DS	Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>) skin	70 (Nandini et al., 2005)
Terrestrial			
CS	Bovine lung	28	(Volpi, 1999)
CS	Bovine trachea	11-31	(Maccari and Volpi, 2003; Mucci et al., 2000; Volpi, 2000, 2004, 2007)
CS	Porcine trachea	18-20	(Maccari and Volpi, 2003; Mucci et al., 2000; Volpi, 2000, 2004)
CS	Porcine nose cartilage	9-13	(Volpi, 2007)
CS	Chicken trachea	8-21	(Maccari and Volpi, 2003; Volpi, 2004, 2007)
DS	Porcine skin	44	(Volpi, 2004)
DS	Pig mucosa	17-40	(Mansour et al., 2009; Santos et al., 2007)
DS	Bovine lung	38	(Volpi, 1999)
DS	Bovine heart	45	(Volpi, 1999)
Marine			
Heparin (HEP) & heparan sulfate (HS)	HEP	Shrimp head (<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i>)	36 (Chavante et al., 2014)
	HEP	Shrimp head (<i>Penaeus brasiliensis</i>)	8 (Dietrich et al., 1999)
	HEP	Clam (<i>Anomalocardia brasiliensis</i>)	32 (Dietrich et al., 1989)

HEP	Clam (<i>Tivela mactroides</i>)	25	(Dietrich et al., 1989)
HEP	Clam (<i>Donax striatus</i>)	20	(Dietrich et al., 1989)
HEP	Clam (<i>Tapes philippinarum</i>)	11	(Cesaretti et al., 2004)
HEP	Crab (<i>Goniopsis cruentata</i>)	19	(Andrade et al., 2013)
HEP	Crab (<i>Ucides cordatus</i>)	9	(Medeiros et al., 2000)
HEP	Sand dollar (<i>Mellita quinquisperforata</i>)	13	(Medeiros et al., 2000)
HEP	Ascidian (<i>Styela plicata</i>)	34	(Santos et al., 2007)
HEP/HS	Shrimp heads (<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i>)	15	(Brito et al., 2014)
HS	Scallop (<i>Nodipecten nodosus</i>)	27	(Gomes et al., 2010)
Terrestrial			
HEP	Mouse	5-25	(Jacobsson and Lindahl, 1987) (Andrade et al., 2013; Brito et al., 2014; Chavante et al., 2014; Frommherz et al., 1991; Santos et al., 2007)
HEP	Pig mucosa	13-18	
HEP	Bovine mucosa	13	(Dietrich et al., 1989)
HEP	Bovine lung	12	(Dietrich et al., 1989)
HS	Bovine pancreas	25	(Andrade et al., 2013; Brito et al., 2014)
HS	Pig mucosa	7-16	Griffin, 1995
HS	Rat organs	12-24	Shi, 2009

Table 2. Molecular weights of chondroitin sulphate (CS), dermatan sulfate (DS), heparin (HEP), heparan sulphate (HEP) and hybrid chains (CS/DS and HEP/HS) isolated from terrestrial and marine animals.

functional tissue. At the same time, the material must be biodegradable and biocompatible. Naturally occurring polymers in cartilage are recognized by cells, facilitating their adherence, and can be easily degraded and eliminated (Camarero-Espinosa et al., 2016). Because of these advantages, natural polymers have been explored for tissue engineering constructs, commonly combined with synthetic polymers or with other biomacromolecules.

In articular cartilage, the natural polymers CS, hyaluronan and collagen are the principal components of a complex structure capable of bearing considerable loads: CS, along with DS and KS chains, is linked to the protein core of aggrecan, the major proteoglycan of cartilage. Aggrecan binds non-covalently with hyaluronan forming a hydrated gel reinforced by a network of collagen fibrils. This structure is the basis for the mechanical properties of cartilage and the electrostatic repulsion forces between GAG chains in aggrecan are fundamental to withstand compression (Muzzarelli et al., 2012). CS accounts for up to 80% of these chains and is the most interesting GAG from the marine perspective. Furthermore, CS chains in aggrecan appear involved in cellular signalling (Fujimoto et al., 2001) and as a result CS has been used to impart bioactivity to synthetic polymers lacking signalling properties (Köwitsch et al., 2016; Ozaltin et al., 2017)

The CS used in tissue engineering is most commonly derived from bovine trachea, although CS from shark cartilage is also employed. Both differ mainly on the disaccharide composition, as bovine CS is rich in A-units (4-sulfated), and shark cartilage CS in C-units (6-sulfated) (Table 1). This difference in sulfation is of no minor importance, as illustrated by the progressive increase with age of 6- over 4S-CS sulfation in human aggrecan (Watanabe et al., 1998),

1 and rare growth disorders in humans resulting from defects in CS sulfation
2 (Thiele et al., 2004; Tuysuz et al., 2009).

3
4 In spite of the importance of CS sulfation, many studies do not specify the CS
5 form used, and very few include CS from more than one source. One such
6 study highlights the impact of the variability of CS in chondrocyte culture, even
7 from the same source. The production of metabolites involved in cartilage
8 degradation and the levels of gene expression of collagen II were studied after
9 addition of porcine and bovine CS. In some cases, opposite results are reported
10 for porcine and bovine CS, possibly related to the disaccharide composition (16-
11 31% of CS-6) and purity (90-99.9%) of CS (TAT et al., 2010). Although marine
12 CS was not included in this study, other works also found differences between
13 CS forms in more complex tissue engineering matrices. CS-A and CS-C added
14 to a 3D-culture of porcine chondrocytes led to different mRNA expression of
15 type-II collagen. This was increased by CS-C from shark but not CS-A from
16 bovine trachea (Nishimoto et al., 2005). Conversely, while CS-A immobilized
17 onto chitosan membranes favoured the differentiation of mesenchymal stem
18 cells (MSC) toward chondrocytes, CS-C had no effect. CS-A also promoted
19 MSC growth to a greater extent than CS-C (Uygun et al., 2009).

20
21 The incorporation of CS-C to tissue engineering matrices is usually made in
22 combination with other natural polymers. In some cases synthetic polymers are
23 used, such as hydrogels made by the complexation of polyethylene glycol and
24 alpha cyclodextrin, which have been employed to deliver CS-C in damaged
25 rabbit joints (Hui et al., 2007). Scaffolds and hydrogels formulated with CS from
26 shark cartilage generally include proteins and natural polysaccharides. Binary
27 combinations with fibrin (Wei et al., 2008), collagen II (Chen et al., 2013) and
28 hyaluronic acid (Ni et al., 2015) are reported, although ternary combinations are
29 more common. These attempt to mimic the native cartilage ECM either with its
30 original main components (collagen II, hyaluronan and CS-C) (Ko et al., 2009)
31 or including gelatin (Balakrishnan et al., 2014; Chang et al., 2003; Hu et al.,
32 2011; Kuo et al., 2015), alginate (Balakrishnan et al., 2014) and chitosan (Kuo
33 et al., 2015; Nair et al., 2015) as substitutes. *In vitro*, the presence of CS-C in
34 the constructs appears to favour the proliferation of chondrocytes (Balakrishnan
35 et al., 2014; Chang et al., 2003; Ko et al., 2009) and differentiation of MSC
36 toward chondrocytes (Nair et al., 2015; Wei et al., 2008) along with ECM
37 secretion. While *in vivo* studies are less common, these seem to confirm that
38 inclusion of CS-C enhance the ability of hydrogels and scaffolds to repair
39 cartilage lesions (Chen et al., 2013; Hui et al., 2007).

40
41 CS with disulfated disaccharide units is also present in cartilage, although
42 representing a small fraction of the total CS. Nevertheless, it might be crucial for
43 chondrogenesis, as revealed by a study comparing the effects of CS containing
44 mono- and disulfated disaccharide units in the differentiation of a
45 prechondrogenic stem cell line. Exogenous CS-E from squid cartilage promoted
46 the chondrogenic differentiation of cells and enhanced the production of
47 collagen II, although it decreased cell proliferation. CS-A and CS-C showed no
48 significant effects in either cell proliferation or differentiation. The authors
49 hypothesize that the positive effects seen are due to the binding of CS-E to
50 fibroblast growth factors and bone morphogenetic proteins (BMPs) (Kawamura

1 et al., 2014). CS-E has shown strong affinity for BMP-4, a growth factor
2 essential for chondrogenic differentiation. In the binding to BMP-4, 4,6
3 disulfated GalNAc present in E-units appears fundamental, since units with
4 sulfation in other positions (CS-B, -C and -D) had considerable lower affinity
5 (Miyazaki et al., 2008). Further than the mere presence of this unit, specific
6 patterns may influence the affinity of CS for chondrogenic growth factors. A
7 recent study immobilized CS tetrasaccharides with different patterns onto chips
8 and analyzed the binding of basic fibroblast growth factor (FGF-2) (Miyachi et
9 al., 2015). This growth factor in combination with BMP-4 has shown to enhance
10 chondrogenic differentiation of human embryonic stem cells (Lee et al., 2013).
11 Tetrasaccharides with stronger affinity for FGF-2 all contained 4,6 disulfated
12 GalNAc, however the disaccharide pattern also had an effect: CS with
13 sequence E+C displayed greater affinity than the inverse sequence C+E.

14
15 Beyond its effect on chondrogenesis, CS-E from squid cartilage was found to
16 improve the mechanical performance of a recently developed double network
17 hydrogel (Zhao et al., 2014). A later study confirmed that the mechanical
18 properties of CS-E hydrogels formed using the same method closely resembled
19 those of native cartilage (Higa et al., 2016). Furthermore, these properties were
20 not significantly reduced at 12 weeks *in vivo*, and although the hydrogel
21 produced initial mild inflammation, this returned to control levels after 4 weeks.
22 In line with the results of Kawamura *et al.*, 2014 (Kawamura et al., 2014), these
23 gels promoted the differentiation of prechondrogenic cells, making them
24 promising materials to build artificial cartilage (Higa et al., 2016).

25 26 **2.2. Nervous system**

27 In the central nervous system (CNS), proteoglycans containing CS, DS and
28 hybrid CS-DS chains are known to interact with growth factors and neurotrophic
29 factors involved in neural migration, axon guidance and neurite outgrowth
30 (Sugahara and Mikami, 2007). These proteoglycans can either act as a barrier
31 to axon growth (Bradbury et al., 2002) or promote neural adhesion, migration
32 and neuritogenesis (Sugahara et al., 2003), apparently regulating the
33 differentiation and proliferation of neuronal cells. In this process, the sulfation
34 patterns of GAG chains seem to directly influence the binding of the
35 proteoglycan to active proteins (Yamada and Sugahara, 2008). Unlike heparin,
36 where a specific pentasaccharide is required for maximum activity, multiple CS
37 sequences can bind to the functional protein. For pleiotrophin, a neurite growth-
38 promoting factor, several motifs containing oversulfated units have been
39 identified during brain development (Bao et al., 2005a). These same motifs
40 present in proteoglycans are proposed to fine-tune the microenvironment of
41 neural stem cells, promoting their proliferation, self-renewal, differentiation to
42 neurons and neurite outgrowth of the latter (Purushothaman et al., 2012). In
43 embryonic pig brain, CS, DS and hybrid CS/DS oligosaccharides containing B,
44 D or E units, commonly found in animals, are reported capable of binding to
45 pleiotrophin (Bao et al., 2005a).

46
47 Marine organisms are a source of oversulfated CS and DS (Table 1). Chains of
48 CS and DS extracted from shark, ascidians, sea urchin, squid and octopus were
49 found to promote neurite outgrowth *in vitro* (Higashi et al., 2015a; Higashi et al.,
50 2015b; Hikino et al., 2003; Nandini et al., 2005; Nandini et al., 2004; Sotogaku

1 et al., 2007; Sugahara and Yamada, 2000). Some of these GAGs share
2 sequences with mammals. CS octasaccharides with sequences Δ C-C-C-C and
3 Δ C-A-D-C isolated from shark cartilage (Nadanaka et al., 1998; Pothacharoen
4 et al., 2007) have also been found in embryonic pig brain, but only the
5 sequence containing D units seems to bind to pleiothrophin (Bao et al., 2005a).
6 Furthermore, monoclonal antibodies designed to inhibit neurite outgrowth
7 promotion in cultured neurons of rodents also recognized as epitopes CS and
8 DS chains containing D units from shark and *Ascidia Nigra* (Malavaki et al.,
9 2008). Beside neurite outgrowth, CS-E from squid has displayed
10 neuroprotective effects in neuronal cell cultures, whereas other CS variants
11 (CS-A, -B, -C and -D) had no effect (Sato et al., 2008). The authors suggest
12 that this effect might be related to the interaction with trophic factors involved in
13 neurite outgrowth and neuroprotection, such as pleiothrophin. This partially
14 contradicts the mentioned study by Bao et al. (Bao et al., 2005b) relating CS-B
15 and -D with pleiothrophin binding.

16
17 Approaches proposed to exploit GAGs as therapeutic agents include delivering
18 neurotrophic factors to stimulate regeneration and using stem cells for
19 regeneration of neurons. Transplanted stem cells are usually seeded in
20 polymeric scaffolds, which can be functionalized with CS to better reproduce the
21 environment of the developing CNS. Further, a bridging scaffold coated with
22 differentially sulphated CS chains forming a gradient could be used to guide
23 axons across the scar tissue to restore neuronal wiring (Swarup et al., 2013). In
24 this line, efforts in nerve regeneration taking advantage of CS properties are
25 promising (Serrano et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2011). Considering the major
26 influence that sulfation patterns seem to have on the development and
27 maintenance of the CNS, the oversulfated CS and DS chains of marine origin
28 hold great potential.

30 **3. Anticoagulant activity**

31 Heparin, commercially extracted from bovine and porcine tissues, has been
32 used since the 1930's as an anticoagulant drug, but safety concerns and
33 increasing demand have spurred interest in finding alternatives. Marine animals
34 could be an alternative, since heparin-like compounds are present in
35 invertebrates, such as echinoderms, ascidians, crustaceans and molluscs.
36 Some invertebrate species contain compounds very similar to mammalian
37 heparin with high affinity for antithrombin, while others are composed of very
38 unusual disaccharide units (Kozłowski, Eliene O. et al., 2011). Regardless of
39 the origin, to become a real alternative marine heparin must prove safety and
40 anticoagulant activity equivalent to that of mammalian sources and be
41 extractable in appreciable quantities. Heparin from pig mucosa is typically
42 extracted with a yield of 0.14 mg/g (Pharma, 2012) and anticoagulant activity of
43 150 USP units/mg (Aldrich), resulting in around 21 USP units (IU) per g of fresh
44 weight (FW). Furthermore, commercial heparin is currently obtained from
45 sources usually considered as waste, most commonly pig intestinal mucosa but
46 also bovine lung and intestine. This character is very advantageous in economic
47 and environmental terms, being therefore a key factor in the viability of
48 alternatives.

1 Also a waste product, low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) has been
2 extracted from the heads of shrimp. Setting pig mucosa as a benchmark, the *in*
3 *vitro* anticoagulant activity of shrimp LMWH is lower (95 IU/mg compared to 150
4 IU/mg). Although *in vivo* test results were similar to bovine heparin (Dietrich et
5 al., 1999), the yield was very low (0.032 mg/g FW compared to 0.14 mg/g FW).
6 Other studies
7 confirm the lower anticoagulant activity of heparin (Brito et al., 2008) and
8 hybrids heparin/HS from shrimp heads with even lower yields (0.0033 mg/g FW)
9 (Brito et al., 2014).
10
11 Bivalve molluscs contain heparin with considerable anticoagulant activity in
12 higher quantities than shrimp heads. Sometimes even higher than in pig
13 mucosa (21 IU/g FW), as is the case of the clam species *Anomalocardia*
14 *brasiliiana* (18-36 IU/g FW) (Dietrich et al., 1989; Santos et al., 2003), *Tridacna*
15 *maxima* (39 IU/g FW) (Arumugam et al., 2008) and *Donnax striatus* (12-27 IU/g
16 FW) (Dietrich et al., 1989). Most interestingly, the clam *Tapes philippinarum* not
17 only showed higher yield and anticoagulant activity than mammalian heparin,
18 but it contained high proportions of the binding site for antithrombin III similar to
19 that of porcine mucosal heparin (Cesaretti et al., 2004). Therefore, clam heparin
20 might appear as an attractive option, with the added advantage that it is
21 possible to grow clams in farms. On the other hand, clams are relatively costly
22 food products and it would be difficult for clam-sourced heparin to compete with
23 heparin from current waste sources.
24
25 Heparin and hybrids with HS are also found in ascidians (Gandra et al., 2000),
26 crabs (Andrade et al., 2013) and sea urchins (Medeiros et al., 2000). In spite of
27 their low anticoagulant activity, some display remarkable antithrombotic activity.
28 Heparin isolated from an ascidian showed antithrombotic activity in an arterial
29 animal model comparable to mammalian heparin and lower bleeding effects
30 (Santos et al., 2007).
31
32 Besides heparin, other GAGs such as HS, DS and CS display anticoagulant
33 properties, but with lower activities than heparin (Ben Mansour et al., 2009;
34 Gomes et al., 2010; Krylov et al., 2011). A rare CS with fucosylated branches
35 extracted from sea cucumber is an exception, some species containing CS
36 chains with potent anticoagulant activity. This activity seems to be similar to that
37 of mammalian heparin in *Stichopus tremulus* and *Isostichopus badionotus* and
38 considerably higher than LMWH from pig mucosa in *Thelenota ananas* (Pomin,
39 2014; Wu et al., 2012). Furthermore, the yield of fucosylated CS in this species
40 was one order of magnitude greater than heparin extracted from pig mucosa,
41 which makes fucosylated CS appear as a promising anticoagulant agent. Major
42 drawbacks are the tendency of native fucosylated CS to produce hypotension
43 and increased bleeding times (Fonseca et al., 2010; Fonseca et al., 2009).
44 Depolymerization has been tried to reduce the side effects, albeit with a
45 concomitant decrease in anticoagulant activity (Li et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2016;
46 Wu et al., 2015; Zhao, L. et al., 2013). Nevertheless, oligosaccharides seem to
47 maintain or even increase anti-Xase and HC-II dependent anti-IIa activities
48 down to a minimum size of around 8.5 kDa, corresponding to 9-10 disaccharide
49 units (Wu et al., 2015; Zhao, L. et al., 2013). Fucosylated CS chains of this
50 length have shown lower bleeding side effects *in vivo* at equivalent

1 antithrombotic doses of low molecular weight heparin (Wu et al., 2015; Zhao et
2 al., 2015). Other undesirable effects, such as platelet and factor XII activation,
3 which causes hypotension, were comparable to that of heparin at Mw below
4 12KDa (Wu et al., 2015).

5
6 Environmental and economic constraints also affect the potential development
7 of fucosylated CS from sea cucumbers into therapeutic products. As is the case
8 of heparin in clams, sea cucumbers are demanded food products with prices
9 increasing up to 12-fold in recent years (Purcell, 2014). As a consequence, the
10 most appreciated sea cucumber species are heavily fished. This is the case of
11 *Thelenota ananas*, currently listed as an endangered species (Conand). These
12 problems could be overcome by new successful strategies for cultivation
13 currently being developed.

14 15 **4. Antiviral**

16 Extracts from a range of marine organisms have shown antiviral activity in both
17 *in vitro* and *in vivo* tests. This activity has been ascribed to a number of
18 molecules, in most cases peptides, glycopeptides and polysaccharides (Cheung
19 et al., 2014; Dang et al., 2015; Vo et al., 2011).

20 Among GAGs, CS-E from squid cartilage has proven a potent antiviral agent
21 against herpes simplex virus (HSV) (Bergefall et al., 2005), T-cell leukaemia
22 virus type I (Jinno-Oue et al., 2013) and the flavivirus dengue (Kato et al.,
23 2010). The antiviral activity seems to be related with interaction of CS-E with
24 attachment proteins of the viral envelope, inhibiting entry into the host cell. In
25 the case of HSV-I, CS-E octasaccharides with at least two consecutive E units
26 seem to be preferred by the viral attachment glycoprotein C (Yamada and
27 Sugahara, 2008).

28
29 Another flavivirus, Japanese encephalopathy viral infection (JEV), was
30 susceptible to CS-E in kidney-derived cell lines from monkey and hamster cells.
31 Surprisingly, CS-E enhanced infection in mouse neuroblastoma cell lines
32 although viral attachment was inhibited. The promotion of infection by CS-E was
33 confirmed *in vivo*: the viral loads of rats infected by JEV injections into the brain
34 were higher if CS-E was injected alongside JEV (Kim et al., 2011).

35
36 CS with fucosylated branches has also attracted attention as an HIV antiviral.
37 Depolymerised fucosylated CS extracted from sea cucumber has shown *in vitro*
38 activity against a range of viral strains, including resistant ones (Huang et al.,
39 2013). The depolymerised fragments seem to maintain similar anti-HIV action
40 with reduced anti-coagulant effects. Again, the action takes place during the
41 early stages of infection, apparently by interaction with an HIV envelope
42 glycoprotein, gp120. This protein binds to cellular receptor CD4, initiating the
43 conformational changes that lead to fusion with the cell. The sulfated fucose
44 branches appear necessary for the antiviral activity, which is also affected by
45 molecular weight and carboxylation (Lian et al., 2013).

46
47 While *in vitro* results of fucosylated CS against HIV show promising, it is
48 questionable whether antiviral activity would be maintained *in vivo*. Other
49 polyanionic HIV entry inhibitors, which were advanced into clinical trials, failed
50 to prove effective against heterosexual HIV-I transmission. This was related to

1 factors not considered in previous development stages, such as the presence of
2 seminal plasma and the concentration and retention of the polyanionic inhibitors
3 (Pirrone et al., 2011).

4 5 **5. Cancer**

6 It is well established that the interaction of cells forming the connective tissue
7 surrounding cancer cells greatly influences tumour growth and cancer
8 progression. Tumour cells release growth factors and cytokines that modify the
9 local environment, which in turn influences the migratory, proliferative and
10 survival capabilities of malignant cells. In this process, the adjacent ECM is
11 remodelled (Afratis et al., 2012).

12
13 GAGs are one of the principal components of the ECM and changes in GAG
14 structure, biosynthesis and degradation enzymes appear involved in cancer
15 progression. Specifically, HS and CS/DS, either free or as proteoglycans, and
16 also hyaluronan, can act as promoters and inhibitors (Afratis et al., 2012).

17
18 HS is known of being capable of direct binding to protein receptors, but in most
19 cases it interacts with growth factors and other signalling molecules as part of
20 proteoglycans (Lindahl and Li, 2009). In this form, HS has shown to influence
21 transformation of epithelial to mesenchymal cells; control of the release of
22 growth factors involved in the promotion and suppression of tumour growth and
23 angiogenesis; and degradation of enzymes related to metastasis (Afratis et al.,
24 2012).

25
26 Heparin seems to act similarly to HS proteoglycans in the inhibition of
27 heparanase, sulfatases and selectin binding, platelet prometastatic effects and
28 growth factor signalling. This is possibly related to the therapeutic effects of
29 heparin seen in the treatment of tumour growth and metastasis in clinical trials
30 and epidemiological studies, which goes apparently beyond its anticoagulant
31 properties (Knelson et al., 2014).

32
33 Few studies have explored the effect of marine heparin on cancer cells, but *in*
34 *vitro* results reported so far are encouraging. Heparin extracted from the sea
35 squirt *Styela plicata* was encapsulated in nanoparticles and assayed *in vitro*
36 using a highly metastatic breast cancer cell line. When compared to
37 encapsulated porcine heparin, the sea squirt formulation showed higher
38 inhibition in cell proliferation, invasion and proteasome activity, which implies
39 increased oxidative stress. *Styela* heparin also induced cell apoptosis, possibly
40 related to increased expression of inflammatory molecules interleukin-6 and -8.
41 The ECM proteolytic enzymes MT1-MMP (matrix metalloproteinase) and uPA
42 (urokinase), involved in cancer cell invasion, were downregulated by *Styela*
43 heparin. Expression of HS cell surface proteoglycans syndecan 1 and 2
44 (overexpressed in several types of cancer) was reduced, but that of syndecan-4
45 (involved in cell adhesion) was increased (Piperigkou et al., 2016). Another *in*
46 *vitro* study reported positive antiproliferative activities of sulphated GAGs
47 extracted from Norway lobster (*Neprops norvegicus*) against human colon
48 carcinoma cells. The sulphated GAGs were composed of HS and DS but were
49 not separated, making it impossible to assign activities to specific compounds
50 (Sayari et al., 2016).

1
2 Similarly to HS, CS and DS are also in most cases in proteoglycan form and
3 influence key cellular processes related to cancer progression, in which, the
4 sulfation pattern appears critical (Afratis et al., 2012). Accordingly, interest in
5 marine GAGs, besides heparin, lay mainly in the effect of chains with
6 uncommon sulfation in terrestrial GAGs and unique structures. Namely, CS/DS
7 with disulfated disaccharide units and fucosylated CS, with most studies looking
8 at effects on processes related to metastasis.

9
10 One such study found that DS chains with disulfated disaccharides extracted
11 from the sea squirts *Styela plicata* (B unit) and *Phallusia nigra* (D unit)
12 attenuated metastasis to the lungs of colon carcinoma and melanoma cells in
13 mice, whereas mammalian DS had no effect. Experiments with P-selectin-
14 deficient mice point out to an effect related to the inhibition of P-selectin, a cell
15 adhesion protein associated to metastasis and cancer-associated thrombosis
16 (Kozłowski, E. O. et al., 2011).

17
18 Also containing disulfated disaccharides, CSE from squid interfered with the
19 motility of mouse breast cancer cells in vitro, while no effect was reported for A,
20 C or D units. The study concludes that CS-E reduces the expression of an ECM
21 pro-metastatic gene (Col1a1) through inhibition of a pro-tumorigenic pathway
22 (Wnt/beta-catenin), resulting in decreased cell migration (Willis and Klüppel,
23 2014).

24 Studies with mice confirm the inhibitory potential of squid CS-E. Osteosarcoma
25 cells capable of forming tumours in the liver of mice contained higher proportion
26 of CS/DS with E-type units. Tumour formation was inhibited by
27 preadministration of CS-E from squid (and not CS-A or CS-C) (Basappa et al.,
28 2009). Similarly, a higher proportion of a CS/DS-E deca-saccharide on the cell
29 surface of Lewis lung carcinoma cells was found to promote metastasis. When
30 injected in mice, preinjection of CS-E from squid cartilage inhibited metastasis
31 to the lungs (Li et al., 2008). A later study revealed that one of the receptors for
32 CS-E chains in the lung was a receptor for advanced glycation end products
33 (RAGE) (Mizumoto et al., 2012), pointing out to RAGE blocking as a strategy for
34 treating pulmonary metastasis.

35
36 GAGs isolated from sea cucumber also appear as inhibitors of metastasis in
37 animal models. Mice preinjected or treated with fucosylated CS and an
38 uncharacterized GAG saw metastasis in the lungs reduced when injected with
39 adenocarcinoma and melanoma cells (Borsig et al., 2007; Zhao, Y. et al., 2013).
40 However, no inhibitory effect on tumour growth was observed in mice implanted
41 with melanoma cells. (Zhang et al., 2009). The inhibitory properties of
42 fucosylated CS are probably related to those of fucoidan (Oliveira et al., 2016),
43 since removal of the fucosylated branches result in loss of activity (Borsig et al.,
44 2007).

45
46 Several mechanisms have been proposed for the anti-metastatic properties of
47 fucosylated CS. Firstly, fucosylated CS, similarly to CS-E, is a ligand antagonist
48 of P- and L-selectins, disrupting the binding of selectins to tumour cell surface
49 receptors (Borsig et al., 2007). Subsequent adhesion to platelets is also
50 disrupted, resulting in inhibition of tumour cell migration (Yue et al., 2015).

1 Second, the anticoagulant properties of sea cucumber GAGs also influence
2 metastasis by targeting TF (Tissue Factor, initiator of coagulation) (Zhao, Y. et
3 al., 2013) and reducing platelet attachment to tumours. Platelet activation and
4 aggregation induced by thrombin was inhibited by GAGs from *Holothuria*
5 *leucospilota* in a recent study. As a consequence, adhesion between platelets
6 and breast cancer cells and adhesion of platelets/cancer cells to fibrinogen was
7 attenuated, decreasing cell migration in vitro (Qian et al., 2015). Finally,
8 angiogenesis processes seem to be also affected by sea cucumber GAGs. A
9 reduction in the proliferation of human umbilical vein endothelial cells
10 (HUVECS) and resulting formation of vessels was observed in *in vitro* and *in*
11 *vivo* assays, apparently related to downregulation of vascular endothelial growth
12 factor (VEGF) (Zhang et al., 2009).

13
14 A common feature of the different mechanisms of fucosylated CS is the
15 downregulation of MMP-2/9 in tumour cells (Qian et al., 2015; Yue et al., 2015;
16 Zhang et al., 2009; Zhao, Y. et al., 2013). These MMPS are matrix
17 metalloproteinases involved in ECM degradation of the basement membrane,
18 which facilitates metastasis. Some studies also report a similar effect on
19 integrins, transmembrane receptors mediating cell-cell and cell-ECM
20 interactions (Qian et al., 2015; Yue et al., 2015).

21 22 **6. Anti-inflammatory**

23
24 Inflammation is a defensive response of the organism to infection or injury,
25 primary achieved through the movement of white blood cells to the site of
26 damage. GAGs, as part of proteoglycans, are involved in this process by
27 participating in the recruitment of leukocytes in blood vessels and facilitating
28 their migration through the endothelium to the injured or infected tissue. The
29 role of GAGs in inflammation is probably behind the anti-inflammatory effects
30 observed in exogenous sulfated GAGs (Pomin, Vitor H., 2015).

31
32 Possibly related to its anticoagulant properties, heparin and its derivatives are
33 considered beneficial for inflammatory diseases, asthma in particular (Mousavi
34 et al., 2015; Oduah et al., 2016). Heparin isolated from marine organisms also
35 appears as an anti-inflammatory agent. The anti-inflammatory activity of a GAG
36 extracted from the shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* was compared to that of
37 porcine heparin, leading to a similar reduction of neutrophil infiltration into the
38 artificially inflamed peritoneal cavity of rats. Both GAGs had a similar structure,
39 but shrimp heparin contained more glucuronic acid and disulfated disaccharide
40 units, resulting in reduced anticoagulant activity. Using human leukocytes, the *in*
41 *vitro* reduction of MMP-9 (metalloproteinase capable of promoting inflammation)
42 activity was also comparable (Brito et al., 2008). Topical administration of
43 mammalian heparin and heparin isolated from the sea squirt *Styela plicata*
44 produced comparable effects on intestinal inflammation in rats suffering colitis
45 induced by colostomy, reducing the accumulation of T-cells and macrophages
46 and the activation of NF- κ B and pERK (mitogen activated protein kinase), key
47 regulators of inflammatory genes. Proinflammatory cytokines interleukin (IL)-1 β ,
48 IL-6 and TNF- α decreased to near normal values with both heparins (Alvarenga
49 Jr et al., 2014). Additionally, heparins isolated from *Styela plicata* and
50 *Litopenaeus vannamei* have shown lower anticoagulant activity than

1 mammalian heparin (Brito et al., 2008; Santos et al., 2007). This is
2 advantageous in terms of related side effects such as bleeding, which are
3 expected to be reduced.

4
5 Also with low anticoagulant activity, CS action on inflammation seems to be
6 once more linked to interactions with cytokines and related regulators, such as
7 NF- κ B. Again, these interactions appear influenced by the sulfation pattern of
8 the CS chains. In an *in vitro* study, inflammation of mouse articular
9 chondrocytes was induced after stimulation with lipopolysaccharides (LPS), the
10 principal component of the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria. The
11 effect of posterior treatment with different GAGs was assessed, including CS-A
12 from bovine trachea and CS-C from shark cartilage. Both CS chains reduced
13 inflammation mediators and apoptosis, although CS-C failed to act upon NO
14 production, a free radical involved in cell damage (Campo et al., 2009).
15 Conversely, a more recent study found that addition of CS-C before inducing
16 inflammation, in this case in mouse bone-marrow derived macrophages using
17 LPS and interferon- γ , produced a reduction in NO production, even to a greater
18 extent than CS-A. The modulatory activities of CS-C from shark cartilage were
19 seen by the reduction of pro-inflammatory cytokines and an increase in the anti-
20 inflammatory cytokine interleukin-10. CS-C also inhibited by 50-60% the nuclear
21 translocation of NF- κ B, known to promote the synthesis of pro-inflammatory
22 cytokines (Tan and Tabata, 2014).

23
24 The effect on inflammation of CS with fucosylated branches occurs apparently
25 through a different mechanism than linear CS. Fucosylated CS isolated from
26 sea cucumber can interfere in the binding of P- and L- selectins on the surface
27 of endothelial cells to sialyl-Lewis X, a tetrasaccharide on the surface of
28 leukocytes (Borsig et al., 2007). This binding is essential for leukocyte tethering
29 and rolling and eventual migration through the endothelial wall (Ley et al.,
30 2007). *In vivo*, fucosylated CS inhibited neutrophil recruitment in induced
31 peritonitis and lung inflammation in mice (Borsig et al., 2007). A later study
32 found that the repeating trisaccharide unit of *Holothuria forskali* fucosylated CS
33 can adopt a conformation similar to that of sialyl-Lewisx. This is possibly the
34 reason for the affinity of fucosylated CS to P- and L-selectins. Although
35 oligosaccharides of fucosylated CS showed milder anti-inflammatory effects *in*
36 *vivo* than the native form, anticoagulant activity was also lower and the
37 fragments were non-toxic (Panagos et al., 2014).

38
39 Similarly to fucosylated CS, DS extracted from sea squirts can also affect
40 selectin binding. DS isolated from *Phallusia nigra* and *Styela plicata* inhibited P-
41 selectin and attenuated the infiltration of inflammatory cells in peritonitis induced
42 in mice (Kozłowski, E. O. et al., 2011). Recently, a novel oversulfated high
43 molecular weight DS was isolated from the gut of *Ascidiella aspersa*.
44 Depolymerized DS proved to be non-toxic and possesses anti-inflammatory
45 properties *in vitro* and *in vivo*, while anticoagulant activity was low (Thomson et
46 al., 2016). This serves to illustrate the potential of marine GAGs as anti-
47 inflammatory agents with reduced undesirable anticoagulation properties.

48 49 **7. Conclusions**

1 Marine GAGs show a wide therapeutic potential in a structure specific manner,
 2 as evidenced by the *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies included in this review. Table 3
 3 tries to summarize the information currently available on the relationship of
 4 structures of marine GAGs and therapeutic properties.
 5
 6

GAG	Source	Cartilage regeneration	Nervous system regeneration	Anticoagulant activity	Antiviral	Cancer	Anti-inflammatory
HEP	Clam			High - <i>A. brasiliensis</i> * (Dietrich et al., 1989; Santos et al., 2003), <i>D. striatus</i> * (Dietrich et al., 1989), <i>T. philippinarum</i> * (Cesaretti et al., 2004), <i>T. maxima</i> * (Arumugam et al., 2008)			
	Shrimp			Low - <i>P. brasiliensis</i> *† (Dietrich et al., 1999); <i>L. vannamei</i> * (Brito et al., 2008; Brito et al., 2014)			Reduction of neutrophil infiltration† and MMPs activity†* - <i>L. vannamei</i> (Brito et al., 2008)
	Sea squirt (<i>S. plicata</i>)			Low* (Gandra et al., 2000; Santos et al., 2007)		Apoptosis of breast cancer cells and inhibition of proliferation* (Piperigkou et al., 2016)	Reduction of inflammation in diversion colitis† - S (Alvarenga Jr et al., 2014)
	Crab			Low* - <i>G. cruentata</i> (Andrade et al., 2013)			
HS	Scallop			Low* - <i>N. nodosus</i> (Gomes et al., 2010)			
HEP/HS	Shrimp			Low* - <i>L. vannamei</i> (Brito et al., 2014)			
CS-C	Shark	Chondrocyte proliferation* (Balakrishnan et al., 2014; Chang et al., 2003; Ko et al., 2009); MSC differentiation* (Nair et al., 2015; Wei et al., 2008); enhancement of construct cartilage repair† (Chen et al., 2013; Hui et al., 2007)					Reduction of inflammation mediators in chondrocytes* (Campo et al., 2009) and bone marrow macrophages* (Tan and Tabata, 2014)
CS-D	Shark		NO* (Sugahara and Yamada, 2000)				
CS-E	Squid	Chondrocyte differentiation* (Higa et al., 2016; Kawamura et al., 2014) Enhanced mechanical properties of hydrogels* (Higa et al., 2016)	Neuro-protection* (Sato et al., 2008)		Entry inhibitor of HSV* (Bergefall et al., 2005), HTLV-I* (Jinno-Oue et al., 2013) and Dengue* (Kato et al., 2010); inhibitor of JEV in kidney cells* 2009; but promotor of infection in the nervous system*† (Kim et al., 2011)	Anti-migratory effects of breast cancer cells* (Willis and Klüppel, 2014); inhibition of formation of liver tumours by osteosarcoma cells†, proliferation and invasive ability* (Basappa et al., 2009); inhibition of metastasis of lung carcinoma cells† (Li et al., 2008)	
CS-K	Octopus		NO*- <i>E. dofleini</i> (Higashi et al., 2015a)				
DS-B	Sea squirt (<i>S. plicata</i>)		NO* (Hikino et al., 2003)			Attenuation of lung metastasis of colon	Attenuation of infiltration of

DS-D	Sea squirt (<i>p. nigra</i>)	NO* (Hikino et al., 2003)			carcinoma and melanoma cells [†] (Kozlowski, E. O. et al., 2011)	inflammatory cells in induced peritonitis [†] (Kozlowski, E. O. et al., 2011)
DS-E	Hagfish notochord	NO*- <i>E. burgeri</i> (Hikino et al., 2003)				
	Embryonic sea urchin	NO*- <i>S. purpuratus</i> (Hikino et al., 2003)				
	Sea squirt (<i>A. aspersa</i>)					Reduced elastase release from neutrophils* and inhibition of neutrophil recruitment [†] (Thomson et al., 2016)
CS/DS	Shark	NO* - <i>I. oxyrinchus</i> and <i>P. glauca</i> (Higashi et al., 2015b; Nandini et al., 2005)				
	Hagfish notochord	NO*- <i>E. burgeri</i> (Nandini et al., 2004)				
Fuco-CS	Sea cucumber		High* - <i>T. ananas</i> , <i>I. badionotus</i> (Pomin, 2014; Wu et al., 2012)	Entry inhibitor of HIV* - <i>T. ananas</i> (Huang et al., 2013; Lian et al., 2013)	Inhibition of lung colonization by adenocarcinoma cells [†] - <i>L. grisea</i> (Borsig et al., 2007)	Inhibition of neutrophil and lung inflammation [†] - <i>L. grisea</i> (Borsig et al., 2007)
Mixed extract	Sea cucumber				Delayed progression of SMM [‡] (Desai et al., 2014)	

Table 3. GAGs in marine animals and therapeutic properties. **in vitro*, [†]*in vivo*, [‡] clinical trial. HEP: heparin, HS: heparan sulfate, CS: chondroitin sulfate, DS: dermatan sulfate, NO: neurite outgrowth, MSC: mesenchymal stem cells, HSV: herpes simplex virus, HTLV-I: T-cell leukaemia virus type I, JEV: Japanese encephalopathy, SMM: asymptomatic multiple myeloma.

Although many promising results have been described, translation into clinical trials is to date very limited. Extracts of shark cartilage were given as complementary treatment to patients suffering advanced breast and colon cancers with discouraging results. There was no difference in survival rate or quality of life for patients receiving shark cartilage over the placebo group (Loprinzi et al., 2005).

A more recent study evaluated the efficacy of an extract made of sea cucumber, sea sponge, shark fin, sea urchin and Sargassum algae, in delaying the progression of asymptomatic multiple myeloma. Results compared favourably with the expected outcomes, but were not conclusive due to limitations of the trial (Desai et al., 2014). In both cases, the extracts are composed of a mixture of molecules, making it impossible to assign the results to GAGs. Especially in the second study, it would be interesting to see the effect of fucosylated CS isolated from other possibly active compounds.

The role of GAGs in cancer remains unclear, and CS/DS and HEP/HS chains appear as both promoters and inhibitors of cancer progression. However, clinical trials and epidemiological studies with mammalian heparin point out to a therapeutic effect in cancer progression and metastasis. Marine heparin

1 extracted from sea squirts seems to influence critical cancer cell functions *in*
2 *vitro*. Also from sea squirts, oversulfated DS has been tested in mice, along with
3 CS/DS-E from squid, with positive effects reducing metastasis. Further *in vivo*
4 tests are needed to confirm the potential of sea squirt HEP and DS, and
5 oversulfated CS/DS from squid and advance to future clinical trials.

6
7 Both inflammation and coagulation play a role in cancer progression and
8 metastasis and particular GAGs are often active in more than one of these
9 processes. Besides the effects seen in metastasis, sea squirt heparin posses
10 anti-inflammatory properties. Shrimp heparin, fucosylated CS from sea
11 cucumber, and CS from shark cartilage are also anti-inflammatory agents *in*
12 *vitro* and *in vivo*, but again, these compounds have not been tested yet in
13 clinical trials. The anticoagulant activity of marine heparin varies widely
14 depending on the source. It is high in clams, but economic reasons prevent it
15 from being an alternative to mammalian heparin. Activity is lower in shrimp and
16 sea squirt heparin and also in CS/DS chains from other invertebrates. This is an
17 advantage for its potential development as drugs for cancer, thrombosis and
18 inflammation because of reduced bleeding side effects. The only possible
19 marine alternative so far is fucosylated CS from sea cucumbers. It still has to
20 prove effective and safe in a clinical setting, but also, its viability dependents on
21 reducing its cost through efficient farming.

22
23 The potent anticoagulant activity of fucosylated CS is a problem for other
24 therapeutic applications and depolymerization has been tried to reduce side
25 effects. This strategy was chosen for its use as anti-inflammatory agent and as
26 antiviral. *In vitro*, depolymerised fucosylated CS has shown activity against HIV
27 resistant strains. Further research is needed and could benefit from the lessons
28 learnt in the development of other promising polianionic HIV entry inhibitors
29 which failed to prove effective in clinical trials. CS-E from squid has also shown
30 *in vitro* activity against a number of viruses, but in the case of Japanese
31 encephalitis, *in vivo* tests confirmed that CS-E promoted the infection. As a
32 consequence, the therapeutic use of CS-E should be approached with caution
33 when neurons are involved because oversulfated CS is known to interact with
34 neurotrophic factors.

35
36 Precisely, this interaction is behind the potential of marine CS and DS chains in
37 neuroregeneration. CS/DS chains can promote or inhibit neuritogenesis, and
38 this is influenced by the sulfation pattern. However, CS-E has shown both
39 effects in neurite extension (Gilbert et al., 2005; Sugahara and Yamada, 2000),
40 maybe because of the presence of specific disaccharide sequences. CS and
41 DS in shark and sea squirt also promote neurite outgrowth, and sequences
42 containing D units seem to be required for the binding to pleiothropin. Although
43 considerable progress has been made, more research is needed to establish
44 motifs in marine GAGs active in the nervous system. Nevertheless, these gaps
45 in knowledge are probably not the only reason for the absence of marine GAGs
46 in neuronal tissue engineering. Greater difficulties exist in the regeneration of
47 the nervous system than in other tissues, such as access to the site of injury
48 and unwanted migration of implanted cells. As the field evolves, it is reasonable
49 to expect the development of applications with marine GAGs.

50

1 In cartilage tissue engineering we see in some way the opposite situation. A
2 number of studies include CS-C, probably not due to its proportion of sulfated
3 units but because it is commercially sourced from shark cartilage. CS sulfation
4 influence chondrogenesis, differentiation, and growth of cells, but little is known
5 about interaction of specific CS sequences and the growth factors involved.
6 Marine CS from shark and squid imparts signalling properties to cartilage
7 engineering constructs and strengthen its structure, as shown by *in vitro* and *in*
8 *vivo* studies. While these results are encouraging, scaffolds incorporating CS
9 have not reached clinical evaluation. Matrices based on collagen, hyaluronan,
10 chitosan and synthetic polymers have been tested in clinical trials with relative
11 success, but generally with mechanical properties inferior to the native tissue. It
12 remains to be seen the contribution of cartilage mimetics including CS,
13 especially that from marine origin, to the clinical application of tissue engineered
14 cartilage.

15
16 Finally, most of the studies included in this review deal with common GAGs
17 found in marine animals. Those in minor quantities, such as keratan sulfate, or
18 with rare disachharide units, such as CS-K from king crab and octopus, draw
19 little attention. More research is needed about the therapeutic potential of these
20 compounds, especially in light of the importance of sulfation in the interaction of
21 GAGs and proteins. In the case of KS, a recent review highlights the potential
22 roles of KS in suppressing cartilage degeneration, combating inflammation
23 processes, reducing radiation-induced apoptosis of lymphoma cells, and
24 inhibiting early phase pathogenesis of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (Pomin, Vitor
25 H, 2015). The cartilage, skin and eyes of fish contain KS, but only a handful of
26 studies have extracted and characterized this GAG.

27 **Acknowledgements**

28 We are grateful to the following projects for support: 0687 NOVOMAR 1 P
29 (POCTEP Programme, EU), iSEAS LIFE13ENV/ES/000131 (LIFE+
30 Programme, EU) and FCT Portugal for the Investigator grant IF/00373/2014.

31 **REFERENCES**

- 32
33
34
35 Afratis, N., Gialeli, C., Nikitovic, D., Tsegenidis, T., Karousou, E., Theocharis, A.D.,
36 Pavão, M.S., Tzanakakis, G.N., Karamanos, N.K., 2012. Glycosaminoglycans: key
37 players in cancer cell biology and treatment. *FEBS Journal* 279(7), 1177-1197.
38 Aldrich, S., Heparin sodium salt from porcine intestinal mucosa. Product specification
39 sheet.
40 Alvarenga Jr, V., Pacheco, R.G., Esposito, C.C., Buongusto, F., Castelo-Branco,
41 M.T.L., Madi, K., Belmiro, C.R., Pavão, M.S.G., de Souza, H.S.P., Schanaider, A.,
42 2014. Ascidian (chordate-tunicate) and mammalian heparin enemas attenuate
43 experimental diversion colitis. *Surgery* 155(2), 217-227.
44 Amado, I.R., Vázquez, J.A., Pastrana, L., Teixeira, J.A., 2016. Cheese whey: A cost-
45 effective alternative for hyaluronic acid production by *Streptococcus zooepidemicus*.
46 *Food Chemistry* 198, 54-61.
47 Andrade, G.P.V., Lima, M.A., de Souza Junior, A.A., Fareed, J., Hoppensteadt, D.A.,
48 Santos, E.A., Chavante, S.F., Oliveira, F.W., Rocha, H.A.O., Nader, H.B., 2013. A
49 heparin-like compound isolated from a marine crab rich in glucuronic acid 2-O-sulfate
50 presents low anticoagulant activity. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 94(1), 647-654.

1 Arumugam, M., Balasubramanian, T., Shanmugam, A., Garg, H., 2008. A comparative
2 study of anticoagulant and antiproliferative activity of fast moving heparin from giant
3 clam *Tridacna maxima* (Roeding, 1798) and green mussel *Perna viridis* (Linnaeus,
4 1758). *J. Appl. Biol. Sci* 2(3), 27-30.

5 Balakrishnan, B., Joshi, N., Jayakrishnan, A., Banerjee, R., 2014. Self-crosslinked
6 oxidized alginate/gelatin hydrogel as injectable, adhesive biomimetic scaffolds for
7 cartilage regeneration. *Acta biomaterialia* 10(8), 3650-3663.

8 Bao, X., Muramatsu, T., Sugahara, K., 2005a. Demonstration of the Pleiotrophin-
9 binding Oligosaccharide Sequences Isolated from Chondroitin Sulfate/Dermatan Sulfate
10 Hybrid Chains of Embryonic Pig Brains. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 280(42),
11 35318-35328.

12 Bao, X., Pavão, M.S.G., dos Santos, J.C., Sugahara, K., 2005b. A Functional Dermatan
13 Sulfate Epitope Containing Iduronate(2-O-sulfate) α 1-3GalNAc(6-O-sulfate)
14 Disaccharide in the Mouse Brain: Demonstration using a novel monoclonal antibody
15 raised against dermatan sulfate of ascidian *Ascidia nigra*. *Journal of Biological*
16 *Chemistry* 280(24), 23184-23193.

17 Basappa, Murugan, S., Sugahara, K.N., Lee, C.M., ten Dam, G.B., van Kuppevelt, T.H.,
18 Miyasaka, M., Yamada, S., Sugahara, K., 2009. Involvement of chondroitin sulfate E in
19 the liver tumor focal formation of murine osteosarcoma cells. *Glycobiology* 19(7), 735-
20 742.

21 Ben Mansour, M., Dhahri, M., Bertholon, I., Ollivier, V., Bataille, I., Ajzenberg, N.,
22 Hassine, M., Jandrot-Perrus, M., Chaubet, F., Maaroufi, R.M., 2009. Characterization of
23 a novel dermatan sulfate with high antithrombin activity from ray skin (*Raja radula*).
24 *Thrombosis Research* 123(6), 887-894.

25 Bergefall, K., Trybala, E., Johansson, M., Uyama, T., Naito, S., Yamada, S., Kitagawa,
26 H., Sugahara, K., Bergström, T., 2005. Chondroitin sulfate characterized by the E-
27 disaccharide unit is a potent inhibitor of herpes simplex virus infectivity and provides
28 the virus binding sites on gro2C cells. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 280(37), 32193-
29 32199.

30 Borsig, L., Wang, L., Cavalcante, M.C.M., Cardilo-Reis, L., Ferreira, P.L., Mourão,
31 P.A.S., Esko, J.D., Pavão, M.S.G., 2007. Selectin Blocking Activity of a Fucosylated
32 Chondroitin Sulfate Glycosaminoglycan from Sea Cucumber: Effect on tumor
33 metastasis and neutrophil recruitment. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 282(20), 14984-
34 14991.

35 Bradbury, E.J., Moon, L.D.F., Popat, R.J., King, V.R., Bennett, G.S., Patel, P.N.,
36 Fawcett, J.W., McMahon, S.B., 2002. Chondroitinase ABC promotes functional
37 recovery after spinal cord injury. *Nature* 416(6881), 636-640.

38 Brito, A.S., Arimatéia, D.S., Souza, L.R., Lima, M.A., Santos, V.O., Medeiros, V.P.,
39 Ferreira, P.A., Silva, R.A., Ferreira, C.V., Justo, G.Z., Leite, E.L., Andrade, G.P.V.,
40 Oliveira, F.W., Nader, H.B., Chavante, S.F., 2008. Anti-inflammatory properties of a
41 heparin-like glycosaminoglycan with reduced anti-coagulant activity isolated from a
42 marine shrimp. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry* 16(21), 9588-9595.

43 Brito, A.S., Cavalcante, R.S., Palhares, L.C.G.F., Hughes, A.J., Andrade, G.P.V., Yates,
44 E.A., Nader, H.B., Lima, M.A., Chavante, S.F., 2014. A non-hemorrhagic hybrid
45 heparin/heparan sulfate with anticoagulant potential. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 99, 372-
46 378.

47 Camarero-Espinosa, S., Rothen-Rutishauser, B., Foster, E.J., Weder, C., 2016. Articular
48 cartilage: from formation to tissue engineering. *Biomaterials Science* 4(5), 734-767.

1 Campo, G.M., Avenoso, A., Campo, S., D'Ascola, A., Traina, P., Samà, D., Calatroni,
2 A., 2009. Glycosaminoglycans modulate inflammation and apoptosis in LPS - treated
3 chondrocytes. *Journal of cellular biochemistry* 106(1), 83-92.

4 Capila, I., Linhardt, R.J., 2002. Heparin-Protein Interactions. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*
5 41(3), 390-412.

6 Cardoso, M.J., Costa, R.R., Mano, J.F., 2016. Marine Origin Polysaccharides in Drug
7 Delivery Systems. *Marine Drugs* 14(2), 34.

8 Cesaretti, M., Luppi, E., Maccari, F., Volpi, N., 2004. Isolation and characterization of a
9 heparin with high anticoagulant activity from the clam *Tapes philippinarum*: evidence
10 for the presence of a high content of antithrombin III binding site. *Glycobiology* 14(12),
11 1275-1284.

12 Conand, C., Gamboa, R. & Purcell, S. 2013. *Thelenota ananas*. The IUCN Red List of
13 Threatened Species 2013: e.T180481A1636021.
14 <http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2013-1.RLTS.T180481A1636021.en>. Downloaded
15 on 17 June 2016.

16 Chang, C.-H., Liu, H.-C., Lin, C.-C., Chou, C.-H., Lin, F.-H., 2003. Gelatin-
17 chondroitin-hyaluronan tri-copolymer scaffold for cartilage tissue engineering.
18 *Biomaterials* 24(26), 4853-4858.

19 Chavante, S.F., Brito, A.S., Lima, M., Yates, E., Nader, H., Guerrini, M., Torri, G.,
20 Bisio, A., 2014. A heparin-like glycosaminoglycan from shrimp containing high levels
21 of 3-O-sulfated d-glucosamine groups in an unusual trisaccharide sequence.
22 *Carbohydrate Research* 390, 59-66.

23 Chen, W.-C., Wei, Y.-H., Chu, I.M., Yao, C.-L., 2013. Effect of chondroitin sulphate C
24 on the in vitro and in vivo chondrogenesis of mesenchymal stem cells in crosslinked
25 type II collagen scaffolds. *Journal of Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine*
26 7(8), 665-672.

27 Cheung, R.C.F., Wong, J.H., Pan, W.L., Chan, Y.S., Yin, C.M., Dan, X.L., Wang, H.X.,
28 Fang, E.F., Lam, S.K., Ngai, P.H.K., Xia, L.X., Liu, F., Ye, X.Y., Zhang, G.Q., Liu,
29 Q.H., Sha, O., Lin, P., Ki, C., Bekhit, A.A., Bekhit, A.E.-D., Wan, D.C.C., Ye, X.J.,
30 Xia, J., Ng, T.B., 2014. Antifungal and antiviral products of marine organisms. *Applied*
31 *Microbiology and Biotechnology* 98(8), 3475-3494.

32 Dang, V.T., Benkendorff, K., Green, T., Speck, P., 2015. Marine Snails and Slugs: a
33 Great Place To Look for Antiviral Drugs. *Journal of Virology* 89(16), 8114-8118.

34 Delbarre-Ladrat, C., Siquin, C., Lebellenger, L., Zykwinska, A., Collic-Jouault, S.,
35 2014. Exopolysaccharides produced by marine bacteria and their applications as
36 glycosaminoglycan-like molecules. *Frontiers in Chemistry* 2(85).

37 Desai, A.V., Lu, M., Marcus, S., Saran, A., Malankar, A., Mazumder, A., 2014. A
38 Phase II Trial of TBL12 Sea Cucumber Extract in Patients with Untreated
39 Asymptomatic Myeloma. *Blood* 124(21), 5733-5733.

40 Dietrich, C.P., Nader, H.B., de Paiva, J.F., Santos, E.A., Holme, K.R., Perlin, A.S.,
41 1989. Heparin in molluscs: chemical, enzymatic degradation and ¹³C and ¹H nmr
42 spectroscopical evidence for the maintenance of the structure through evolution.
43 *International journal of biological macromolecules* 11(6), 361-366.

44 Dietrich, C.P., Paiva, J.F., Castro, R.A.B., Chavante, S.F., Jeske, W., Fareed, J., Gorin,
45 P.A.J., Mendes, A., Nader, H.B., 1999. Structural features and anticoagulant activities
46 of a novel natural low molecular weight heparin from the shrimp *Penaeus brasiliensis*.
47 *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - General Subjects* 1428(2-3), 273-283.

48 Fonseca, R.J., Oliveira, S.-N., Pomin, V.H., Mecawi, A.S., Araujo, I.G., Mourão, P.A.,
49 2010. Effects of oversulfated and fucosylated chondroitin sulfates on coagulation.
50 *Thrombosis and haemostasis* 103(5), 994-1004.

1 Fonseca, R.J.C., Santos, G.R.C., Mourão, P.A.S., 2009. Effects of polysaccharides
2 enriched in 2,4-disulfated fucose units on coagulation, thrombosis and bleeding:
3 Practical and conceptual implications. *Thrombosis and haemostasis* 102(5), 829-836.
4 Frommherz, K.J., Faller, B., Bieth, J.G., 1991. Heparin strongly decreases the rate of
5 inhibition of neutrophil elastase by alpha 1-proteinase inhibitor. *Journal of Biological*
6 *Chemistry* 266(23), 15356-15362.
7 Fujimoto, T., Kawashima, H., Tanaka, T., Hirose, M., Toyama-Sorimachi, N.,
8 Matsuzawa, Y., Miyasaka, M., 2001. CD44 binds a chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan,
9 aggrecan. *International Immunology* 13(3), 359-366.
10 Gandra, M., Cavalcante, M.C., Pavão, M.S., 2000. Anticoagulant sulfated
11 glycosaminoglycans in the tissues of the primitive chordate *Styela plicata* (Tunicata).
12 *Glycobiology* 10(12), 1333-1340.
13 Gilbert, R.J., McKeon, R.J., Darr, A., Calabro, A., Hascall, V.C., Bellamkonda, R.V.,
14 2005. CS-4,6 is differentially upregulated in glial scar and is a potent inhibitor of
15 neurite extension. *Molecular and Cellular Neuroscience* 29(4), 545-558.
16 Gomes, A.M., Kozłowski, E.O., Pomin, V.H., de Barros, C.M., Zaganeli, J.L., Pavão,
17 M.S.G., 2010. Unique Extracellular Matrix Heparan Sulfate from the Bivalve
18 *Nodipecten nodosus* (Linnaeus, 1758) Safely Inhibits Arterial Thrombosis after
19 Photochemically Induced Endothelial Lesion. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 285(10),
20 7312-7323.
21 Gulati, K., Poluri, K.M., 2016. Mechanistic and therapeutic overview of
22 glycosaminoglycans: the unsung heroes of biomolecular signaling. *Glycoconjugate*
23 *Journal* 33(1), 1-17.
24 Higa, K., Kitamura, N., Kurokawa, T., Goto, K., Wada, S., Nonoyama, T., Kanaya, F.,
25 Sugahara, K., Gong, J.P., Yasuda, K., 2016. Fundamental biomaterial properties of
26 tough glycosaminoglycan-containing double network hydrogels newly developed using
27 the molecular stent method. *Acta biomaterialia* 43, 38-49.
28 Higashi, K., Okamoto, Y., Mukuno, A., Wakai, J., Hosoyama, S., Linhardt, R.J., Toida,
29 T., 2015a. Functional chondroitin sulfate from *Enteroctopus dofleini* containing a 3-O-
30 sulfo glucuronic acid residue. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 134, 557-565.
31 Higashi, K., Takeuchi, Y., Mukuno, A., Tomitori, H., Miya, M., Linhardt, R.J., Toida,
32 T., 2015b. Composition of Glycosaminoglycans in Elasmobranchs including Several
33 Deep-Sea Sharks: Identification of Chondroitin/Dermatan Sulfate from the Dried Fins
34 of *Isurus oxyrinchus* and *Prionace glauca*. *PLoS ONE* 10(3), e0120860.
35 Hikino, M., Mikami, T., Faissner, A., Vilela-Silva, A.-C.E.S., Pavão, M.S.G., Sugahara,
36 K., 2003. Oversulfated Dermatan Sulfate Exhibits Neurite Outgrowth-promoting
37 Activity toward Embryonic Mouse Hippocampal Neurons: Implications of dermatan
38 sulfate in neuritogenesis in the brain. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 278(44), 43744-
39 43754.
40 Hileman, R.E., Fromm, J.R., Weiler, J.M., Linhardt, R.J., 1998. Glycosaminoglycan-
41 protein interactions: definition of consensus sites in glycosaminoglycan binding
42 proteins. *BioEssays* 20(2), 156-167.
43 Hu, X., Li, D., Zhou, F., Gao, C., 2011. Biological hydrogel synthesized from
44 hyaluronic acid, gelatin and chondroitin sulfate by click chemistry. *Acta biomaterialia*
45 7(4), 1618-1626.
46 Huang, N., Wu, M.-Y., Zheng, C.-B., Zhu, L., Zhao, J.-H., Zheng, Y.-T., 2013. The
47 depolymerized fucosylated chondroitin sulfate from sea cucumber potently inhibits HIV
48 replication via interfering with virus entry. *Carbohydrate Research* 380, 64-69.

1 Hui, J.H., Chan, S.-W., Li, J., Goh, J.C.H., Li, L., Ren, X.F., Lee, E.H., 2007. Intra-
2 articular delivery of chondroitin sulfate for the treatment of joint defects in rabbit
3 model. *Journal of Molecular Histology* 38(5), 483-489.

4 Ito, M., Kitamikado, M., Yamagata, T., 1984. Isolation and characterization of an
5 asparagine-linked keratan sulfate from the skin of a marine teleost, *Scomber japonicus*.
6 *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - General Subjects* 797(2), 221-230.

7 Jacobsson, K.G., Lindahl, U., 1987. Degradation of heparin proteoglycan in cultured
8 mouse mastocytoma cells. *Biochemical Journal* 246(2), 409-415.

9 Jinno-Oue, A., Tanaka, A., Shimizu, N., Mori, T., Sugiura, N., Kimata, K., Isomura, H.,
10 Hoshino, H., 2013. Inhibitory effect of chondroitin sulfate type e on the binding step of
11 human T-cell leukemia virus type 1. *AIDS Research and Human Retroviruses* 29(3),
12 621-629.

13 Kato, D., Era, S., Watanabe, I., Arihara, M., Sugiura, N., Kimata, K., Suzuki, Y.,
14 Morita, K., Hidari, K.I.P.J., Suzuki, T., 2010. Antiviral activity of chondroitin sulphate
15 E targeting dengue virus envelope protein. *Antiviral Research* 88(2), 236-243.

16 Kawamura, D., Funakoshi, T., Mizumoto, S., Sugahara, K., Iwasaki, N., 2014. Sulfation
17 patterns of exogenous chondroitin sulfate affect chondrogenic differentiation of ATDC5
18 cells. *Journal of Orthopaedic Science* 19(6), 1028-1035.

19 Kim, E., Okumura, M., Sawa, H., Miyazaki, T., Fujikura, D., Yamada, S., Sugahara, K.,
20 Sasaki, M., Kimura, T., 2011. Paradoxical effects of chondroitin sulfate-E on Japanese
21 encephalitis viral infection. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*
22 409(4), 717-722.

23 Knelson, E.H., Nee, J.C., Blobe, G.C., 2014. Heparan sulfate signaling in cancer.
24 *Trends in Biochemical Sciences* 39(6), 277-288.

25 Ko, C.-S., Huang, J.-P., Huang, C.-W., Chu, I.M., 2009. Type II collagen-chondroitin
26 sulfate-hyaluronan scaffold cross-linked by genipin for cartilage tissue engineering.
27 *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering* 107(2), 177-182.

28 Köwitsch, A., Niepel, M.S., Michanetzis, G.P.A., Missirlis, Y.F., Groth, T., 2016.
29 Effect of Immobilized Thiolated Glycosaminoglycans on Fibronectin Adsorption and
30 Behavior of Fibroblasts. *Macromolecular Bioscience* 16(3), 381-394.

31 Kozłowski, E.O., Gomes, A.M., Silva, C.S., Pereira, M.S., de Vilela Silva, A.C.E.S.,
32 Pavão, M.S.G., 2011. Structure and Biological Activities of Glycosaminoglycan
33 Analogs from Marine Invertebrates: New Therapeutic Agents?, in: Pavão, S.G.M. (Ed.)
34 *Glycans in Diseases and Therapeutics*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg,
35 pp. 159-184.

36 Kozłowski, E.O., Pavao, M.S.G., Borsig, L., 2011. Ascidian dermatan sulfates attenuate
37 metastasis, inflammation and thrombosis by inhibition of P-selectin. *Journal of*
38 *Thrombosis and Haemostasis* 9(9), 1807-1815.

39 Krylov, V.B., Grachev, A.A., Ustyuzhanina, N.E., Ushakova, N.A., Preobrazhenskaya,
40 M.E., Kozlova, N.I., Portsel, M.N., Konovalova, I.N., Novikov, V.Y., Siebert, H.-C.,
41 Shashkov, A.S., Nifantiev, N.E., 2011. Preliminary structural characterization, anti-
42 inflammatory and anticoagulant activities of chondroitin sulfates from marine fish
43 cartilage. *Russian Chemical Bulletin* 60(4), 746.

44 Kuo, C.-Y., Chen, C.-H., Hsiao, C.-Y., Chen, J.-P., 2015. Incorporation of chitosan in
45 biomimetic gelatin/chondroitin-6-sulfate/hyaluronan cryogel for cartilage tissue
46 engineering. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 117, 722-730.

47 Lee, T.-J., Jang, J., Kang, S., Jin, M., Shin, H., Kim, D.-W., Kim, B.-S., 2013.
48 Enhancement of osteogenic and chondrogenic differentiation of human embryonic stem
49 cells by mesodermal lineage induction with BMP-4 and FGF2 treatment. *Biochemical*
50 *and Biophysical Research Communications* 430(2), 793-797.

1 Ley, K., Laudanna, C., Cybulsky, M.I., Nourshargh, S., 2007. Getting to the site of
2 inflammation: the leukocyte adhesion cascade updated. *Nat Rev Immunol* 7(9), 678-
3 689.

4 Li, F., ten Dam, G.B., Murugan, S., Yamada, S., Hashiguchi, T., Mizumoto, S., Oguri,
5 K., Okayama, M., van Kuppevelt, T.H., Sugahara, K., 2008. Involvement of Highly
6 Sulfated Chondroitin Sulfate in the Metastasis of the Lewis Lung Carcinoma Cells. *The*
7 *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 283(49), 34294-34304.

8 Li, J.-h., Li, S., Zhi, Z.-j., Yan, L.-f., Ye, X.-q., Ding, T., Yan, L., Linhardt, R., Chen,
9 S.-g., 2016. Depolymerization of Fucosylated Chondroitin Sulfate with a Modified
10 Fenton-System and Anticoagulant Activity of the Resulting Fragments. *Marine Drugs*
11 14(9), 170.

12 Li, J.P., Kusche-Gullberg, M., 2016. Chapter Six - Heparan Sulfate: Biosynthesis,
13 Structure, and Function, in: Kwang, W.J. (Ed.) *International Review of Cell and*
14 *Molecular Biology*. Academic Press, pp. 215-273.

15 Lian, W., Wu, M., Huang, N., Gao, N., Xiao, C., Li, Z., Zhang, Z., Zheng, Y., Peng, W.,
16 Zhao, J., 2013. Anti-HIV-1 activity and structure–activity-relationship study of a
17 fucosylated glycosaminoglycan from an echinoderm by targeting the conserved CD4
18 induced epitope. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - General Subjects* 1830(10),
19 4681-4691.

20 Lindahl, U., Li, J.p., 2009. Chapter 3 Interactions Between Heparan Sulfate and
21 Proteins—Design and Functional Implications, *International Review of Cell and*
22 *Molecular Biology*. Academic Press, pp. 105-159.

23 Liu, J., Shriver, Z., Pope, R.M., Thorp, S.C., Duncan, M.B., Copeland, R.J., Raska,
24 C.S., Yoshida, K., Eisenberg, R.J., Cohen, G., Linhardt, R.J., Sasisekharan, R., 2002.
25 Characterization of a Heparan Sulfate Octasaccharide That Binds to Herpes Simplex
26 Virus Type 1 Glycoprotein D. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 277(36), 33456-33467.

27 Liu, X., Hao, J., Shan, X., Zhang, X., Zhao, X., Li, Q., Wang, X., Cai, C., Li, G., Yu,
28 G., 2016. Antithrombotic activities of fucosylated chondroitin sulfates and their
29 depolymerized fragments from two sea cucumbers. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 152, 343-
30 350.

31 Loprinzi, C.L., Levitt, R., Barton, D.L., Sloan, J.A., Atherton, P.J., Smith, D.J., Dakhil,
32 S.R., Moore, D.F., Krook, J.E., Rowland, K.M., 2005. Evaluation of shark cartilage in
33 patients with advanced cancer. *Cancer* 104(1), 176-182.

34 Maccari, F., Ferrarini, F., Volpi, N., 2010. Structural characterization of chondroitin
35 sulfate from sturgeon bone. *Carbohydrate Research* 345(11), 1575-1580.

36 Maccari, F., Galeotti, F., Volpi, N., 2015. Isolation and structural characterization of
37 chondroitin sulfate from bony fishes. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 129, 143-147.

38 Maccari, F., Volpi, N., 2003. Direct and specific recognition of glycosaminoglycans by
39 antibodies after their separation by agarose gel electrophoresis and blotting on
40 cetylpyridinium chloride - treated nitrocellulose membranes. *Electrophoresis* 24(9),
41 1347-1352.

42 Malavaki, C., Mizumoto, S., Karamanos, N., Sugahara, K., 2008. Recent Advances in
43 the Structural Study of Functional Chondroitin Sulfate and Dermatan Sulfate in Health
44 and Disease. *Connective Tissue Research* 49(3-4), 133-139.

45 Mansour, M.B., Dhahri, M., Bertholon, I., Ollivier, V., Bataille, I., Ajzenberg, N.,
46 Hassine, M., Jandrot-Perrus, M., Chaubet, F., Maaroufi, R.M., 2009. Characterization of
47 a novel dermatan sulfate with high antithrombin activity from ray skin (*Raja radula*).
48 *Thrombosis Research* 123(6), 887-894.

1 Martel-Pelletier, J., Farran, A., Montell, E., Vergés, J., Pelletier, J.-P., 2015.
2 Discrepancies in Composition and Biological Effects of Different Formulations of
3 Chondroitin Sulfate. *Molecules* 20(3), 4277.
4 Medeiros, G.F., Mendes, A., Castro, R.A.B., Baú, E.C., Nader, H.B., Dietrich, C.P.,
5 2000. Distribution of sulfated glycosaminoglycans in the animal kingdom: widespread
6 occurrence of heparin-like compounds in invertebrates. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta*
7 (BBA) - General Subjects 1475(3), 287-294.
8 Miyachi, K., Wakao, M., Suda, Y., 2015. Syntheses of chondroitin sulfate
9 tetrasaccharide structures containing 4,6-disulfate patterns and analysis of their
10 interaction with glycosaminoglycan-binding protein. *Bioorganic & Medicinal*
11 *Chemistry Letters* 25(7), 1552-1555.
12 Miyazaki, T., Miyauchi, S., Tawada, A., Anada, T., Matsuzaka, S., Suzuki, O., 2008.
13 Oversulfated chondroitin sulfate-E binds to BMP-4 and enhances osteoblast
14 differentiation. *Journal of Cellular Physiology* 217(3), 769-777.
15 Mizumoto, S., Takahashi, J., Sugahara, K., 2012. Receptor for Advanced Glycation End
16 Products (RAGE) Functions as Receptor for Specific Sulfated Glycosaminoglycans, and
17 Anti-RAGE Antibody or Sulfated Glycosaminoglycans Delivered in Vivo Inhibit
18 Pulmonary Metastasis of Tumor Cells. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 287(23), 18985-
19 18994.
20 Mousavi, S., Moradi, M., Khorshidahmad, T., Motamedi, M., 2015. Anti-Inflammatory
21 Effects of Heparin and Its Derivatives: A Systematic Review. *Advances in*
22 *Pharmacological Sciences* 2015, 14.
23 Mucci, A., Schenetti, L., Volpi, N., 2000. ¹H and ¹³C nuclear magnetic resonance
24 identification and characterization of components of chondroitin sulfates of various
25 origin. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 41(1), 37-45.
26 Murado, M., Montemayor, M.I., Cabo, M., Vázquez, J.A., González, M., 2012.
27 Optimization of extraction and purification process of hyaluronic acid from fish eyeball.
28 *Food and Bioproducts Processing* 90(3), 491-498.
29 Muzzarelli, R.A., Greco, F., Busilacchi, A., Sollazzo, V., Gigante, A., 2012. Chitosan,
30 hyaluronan and chondroitin sulfate in tissue engineering for cartilage regeneration: A
31 review. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 89(3), 723-739.
32 Nadanaka, S., Clement, A., Masayama, K., Faissner, A., Sugahara, K., 1998.
33 Characteristic Hexasaccharide Sequences in Octasaccharides Derived from Shark
34 Cartilage Chondroitin Sulfate D with a Neurite Outgrowth Promoting Activity. *Journal*
35 *of Biological Chemistry* 273(6), 3296-3307.
36 Nair, M.B., Baranwal, G., Vijayan, P., Keyan, K.S., Jayakumar, R., 2015. Composite
37 hydrogel of chitosan–poly(hydroxybutyrate-co-valerate) with chondroitin sulfate
38 nanoparticles for nucleus pulposus tissue engineering. *Colloids and Surfaces B:*
39 *Biointerfaces* 136, 84-92.
40 Nandini, C.D., Itoh, N., Sugahara, K., 2005. Novel 70-kDa Chondroitin
41 Sulfate/Dermatan Sulfate Hybrid Chains with a Unique Heterogenous Sulfation Pattern
42 from Shark Skin, Which Exhibit Neuritogenic Activity and Binding Activities for
43 Growth Factors and Neurotrophic Factors. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 280(6),
44 4058-4069.
45 Nandini, C.D., Mikami, T., Ohta, M., Itoh, N., Akiyama-Nambu, F., Sugahara, K.,
46 2004. Structural and Functional Characterization of Oversulfated Chondroitin
47 Sulfate/Dermatan Sulfate Hybrid Chains from the Notochord of Hagfish: Neuritogenic
48 and binding activities for growth factors and neurotrophic factors. *Journal of Biological*
49 *Chemistry* 279(49), 50799-50809.

1 Ni, Y., Tang, Z., Cao, W., Lin, H., Fan, Y., Guo, L., Zhang, X., 2015. Tough and elastic
2 hydrogel of hyaluronic acid and chondroitin sulfate as potential cell scaffold materials.
3 *International journal of biological macromolecules* 74, 367-375.

4 Nishimoto, S., Takagi, M., Wakitani, S., Nihira, T., Yoshida, T., 2005. Effect of
5 chondroitin sulfate and hyaluronic acid on gene expression in a three-dimensional
6 culture of chondrocytes. *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering* 100(1), 123-126.

7 Novoa-Carballal, R., Pérez-Martín, R., Blanco, M., Sotelo, C.G., Fassini, D., Nunes, C.,
8 Coimbra, M.A., Silva, T.H., Reis, R.L., Vázquez, J.A., 2017. By-products of
9 *Scyliorhinus canicula*, *Prionace glauca* and *Raja clavata*: A valuable source of
10 predominantly 6S sulfated chondroitin sulfate. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 157, 31-37.

11 Oduah, E., Linhardt, R., Sharfstein, S., 2016. Heparin: Past, Present, and Future.
12 *Pharmaceuticals* 9(3), 38.

13 Oliveira, C., Ferreira, A.S., Novoa-Carballal, R., Nunes, C., Pashkuleva, I., Neves,
14 N.M., Coimbra, M.A., Reis, R.L., Martins, A., Silva, T.H., 2016. The Key Role of
15 Sulfation and Branching on Fucoidan Antitumor Activity. *Macromolecular Bioscience*,
16 1600340-n/a.

17 Ozaltin, K., Lehocký, M., Kuceková, Z., Humpolíček, P., Sába, P., 2017. A novel
18 multistep method for chondroitin sulphate immobilization and its interaction with
19 fibroblast cells. *Materials Science and Engineering: C* 70, Part 1, 94-100.

20 Panagos, C.G., Thomson, D.S., Moss, C., Hughes, A.D., Kelly, M.S., Liu, Y., Chai, W.,
21 Venkatasamy, R., Spina, D., Page, C.P., Hogwood, J., Woods, R.J., Mulloy, B.,
22 Bavington, C.D., Uhrin, D., 2014. Fucosylated Chondroitin Sulfates from the Body
23 Wall of the Sea Cucumber *Holothuria forskali*: Conformation, selectin binding, and
24 biological activity. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 289(41), 28284-28298.

25 Pavao, M.S., Aiello, K.R., Werneck, C.C., Silva, L.C.F., Valente, A.-P., Mulloy, B.,
26 Colwell, N.S., Tollefsen, D.M., Mourão, P.A., 1998. Highly sulfated dermatan sulfates
27 from ascidians structure versus anticoagulant activity of these glycosaminoglycans.
28 *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 273(43), 27848-27857.

29 Petitou, M., Casu, B., Lindahl, U., 2003. 1976–1983, a critical period in the history of
30 heparin: the discovery of the antithrombin binding site. *Biochimie* 85(1–2), 83-89.

31 Pharma, L., 2012. Green Accounts Esbjerg 2012.

32 Piperigkou, Z., Karamanou, K., Afratis, N.A., Bouris, P., Gialeli, C., Belmiro, C.L.R.,
33 Pavão, M.S.G., Vynios, D.H., Tsatsakis, A.M., 2016. Biochemical and toxicological
34 evaluation of nano-heparins in cell functional properties, proteasome activation and
35 expression of key matrix molecules. *Toxicology Letters* 240(1), 32-42.

36 Pirrone, V., Wigdahl, B., Krebs, F.C., 2011. The rise and fall of polyanionic inhibitors
37 of the human immunodeficiency virus type 1. *Antiviral Research* 90(3), 168-182.

38 Place, E.S., Evans, N.D., Stevens, M.M., 2009. Complexity in biomaterials for tissue
39 engineering. *Nat Mater* 8(6), 457-470.

40 Pomin, V.H., 2014. Holothurian fucosylated chondroitin sulfate. *Marine Drugs* 12(1),
41 232-254.

42 Pomin, V.H., 2015. Keratan sulfate: an up-to-date review. *International journal of*
43 *biological macromolecules* 72, 282-289.

44 Pomin, V.H., 2015. Sulfated glycans in inflammation. *European Journal of Medicinal*
45 *Chemistry* 92, 353-369.

46 Pothacharoen, P., Kalayanamitra, K., Deepa, S.S., Fukui, S., Hattori, T., Fukushima, N.,
47 Hardingham, T., Kongtawelert, P., Sugahara, K., 2007. Two Related but Distinct
48 Chondroitin Sulfate Mimotope Octasaccharide Sequences Recognized by Monoclonal
49 Antibody WF6. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 282(48), 35232-35246.

1 Purcell, S.W., 2014. Value, Market Preferences and Trade of Beche-De-Mer from
2 Pacific Island Sea Cucumbers. PLoS ONE 9(4), e95075.

3 Purushothaman, A., Sugahara, K., Faissner, A., 2012. Chondroitin Sulfate “Wobble
4 Motifs” Modulate Maintenance and Differentiation of Neural Stem Cells and Their
5 Progeny. The Journal of Biological Chemistry 287(5), 2935-2942.

6 Qian, W., Tao, L., Wang, Y., Zhang, F., Li, M., Huang, S., Wang, A., Chen, W., Yue,
7 Z., Chen, L., 2015. Downregulation of integrins in cancer cells and anti-platelet
8 properties are involved in Holothurian glycosaminoglycan-mediated disruption of the
9 interaction of cancer cells and platelets in hematogenous metastasis. Journal of vascular
10 research 52(3), 197-209.

11 Rabenstein, D.L., 2002. Heparin and heparan sulfate: structure and function. Natural
12 Product Reports 19(3), 312-331.

13 Ralphs, J.R., Benjamin, M., 1992. Chondroitin and keratan sulphate in the epidermal
14 club cells of teleosts. Journal of Fish Biology 40(3), 473-475.

15 Santos, E.A., Rocha, L.R., Pereira, N.M., Andrade, G.P., Nader, H.B., Dietrich, C.P.,
16 2003. Mast cells are present in epithelial layers of different tissues of the mollusc
17 *Anomalocardia brasiliiana*. In situ characterization of heparin and a correlation of
18 heparin and histamine concentration. The Histochemical Journal 34(11-12), 553-558.

19 Santos, J.C., Mesquita, J.M.F., Belmiro, C.L.R., da Silveira, C.B.M., Viskov, C.,
20 Mourier, P.A., Pavão, M.S.G., 2007. Isolation and characterization of a heparin with
21 low antithrombin activity from the body of *Styela plicata* (Chordata-Tunicata). Distinct
22 effects on venous and arterial models of thrombosis. Thrombosis Research 121(2), 213-
23 223.

24 Sato, Y., Nakanishi, K., Tokita, Y., Kakizawa, H., Ida, M., Maeda, H., Matsui, F.,
25 Aono, S., Saito, A., Kuroda, Y., 2008. A highly sulfated chondroitin sulfate preparation,
26 CS - E, prevents excitatory amino acid - induced neuronal cell death. Journal of
27 Neurochemistry 104(6), 1565-1576.

28 Sayari, N., Balti, R., Ben Mansour, M., Ben Amor, I., Graiet, I., Gargouri, J., Bougatef,
29 A., 2016. Anticoagulant properties and cytotoxic effect against HCT116 human colon
30 cell line of sulfated glycosaminoglycans isolated from the Norway lobster (*Nephrops*
31 *norvegicus*) shell. Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy 80, 322-330.

32 Senni, K., Pereira, J., Gueniche, F., Delbarre-Ladrat, C., Sinquin, C., Ratiskol, J.,
33 Godeau, G., Fischer, A.-M., Helley, D., Collic-Jouault, S., 2011. Marine
34 polysaccharides: a source of bioactive molecules for cell therapy and tissue engineering.
35 Marine Drugs 9(9), 1664-1681.

36 Serrano, M.C., Nardecchia, S., García-Rama, C., Ferrer, M.L., Collazos-Castro, J.E., del
37 Monte, F., Gutiérrez, M.C., 2014. Chondroitin sulphate-based 3D scaffolds containing
38 MWCNTs for nervous tissue repair. Biomaterials 35(5), 1543-1551.

39 Shuhei, Y., Kazuyuki, S., 2008. Potential Therapeutic Application of Chondroitin
40 Sulfate/Dermatan Sulfate. Current Drug Discovery Technologies 5(4), 289-301.

41 Shukla, D., Liu, J., Blaiklock, P., Shworak, N.W., Bai, X., Esko, J.D., Cohen, G.H.,
42 Eisenberg, R.J., Rosenberg, R.D., Spear, P.G., 1999. A Novel Role for 3-O-Sulfated
43 Heparan Sulfate in Herpes Simplex Virus 1 Entry. Cell 99(1), 13-22.

44 Silva, T.H., Alves, A., Ferreira, B., Oliveira, J.M., Reys, L., Ferreira, R., Sousa, R.,
45 Silva, S., Mano, J., Reis, R., 2012. Materials of marine origin: a review on polymers and
46 ceramics of biomedical interest. International Materials Reviews 57(5), 276-306.

47 Soares da Costa, D., Reis, R.L., Pashkuleva, I., 2017. Sulfation of Glycosaminoglycans
48 and Its Implications in Human Health and Disorders. Annual Review of Biomedical
49 Engineering 19(1).

1 Sotogaku, N., Tully, S.E., Gama, C.I., Higashi, H., Tanaka, M., Hsieh-Wilson, L.C.,
2 Nishi, A., 2007. Activation of phospholipase C pathways by a synthetic chondroitin
3 sulfate-E tetrasaccharide promotes neurite outgrowth of dopaminergic neurons. *Journal*
4 *of Neurochemistry* 103(2), 749-760.

5 Souza, A.R.C., Kozłowski, E.O., Cerqueira, V.R., Castelo-Branco, M.T.L., Costa, M.L.,
6 Pavão, M.S.G., 2007. Chondroitin sulfate and keratan sulfate are the major
7 glycosaminoglycans present in the adult zebrafish *Danio rerio* (Chordata-Cyprinidae).
8 *Glycoconjugate Journal* 24(9), 521-530.

9 Sugahara, K., Kitagawa, H., 2002. Heparin and Heparan Sulfate Biosynthesis. *IUBMB*
10 *Life* 54(4), 163-175.

11 Sugahara, K., Mikami, T., 2007. Chondroitin/dermatan sulfate in the central nervous
12 system. *Current Opinion in Structural Biology* 17(5), 536-545.

13 Sugahara, K., Mikami, T., Uyama, T., Mizuguchi, S., Nomura, K., Kitagawa, H., 2003.
14 Recent advances in the structural biology of chondroitin sulfate and dermatan sulfate.
15 *Current Opinion in Structural Biology* 13(5), 612-620.

16 Sugahara, K., Tanaka, Y., Yamada, S., Seno, N., Kitagawa, H., Haslam, S.M., Morris,
17 H.R., Dell, A., 1996. Novel Sulfated Oligosaccharides Containing 3-O-Sulfated
18 Glucuronic Acid from King Crab Cartilage Chondroitin Sulfate K: Unexpected
19 degradation by chondroitinase ABC. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 271(43), 26745-
20 26754.

21 Sugahara, K., Yamada, S., 2000. Structure and Function of Oversulfated Chondroitin
22 Sulfate Variants
23 Unique Sulfation Patterns and Neuroregulatory Activities. *Trends in Glycoscience and*
24 *Glycotechnology* 12(67), 321-349.

25 Swarup, V.P., Mencio, C.P., Hlady, V., Kuberan, B., 2013. Sugar glues for broken
26 neurons. *Biomol Concepts* 4(3), 233-257.

27 Tamura, J.-i., Arima, K., Imazu, A., Tsutsumishita, N., Fujita, H., Yamane, M.,
28 Matsumi, Y., 2009. Sulfation patterns and the amounts of chondroitin sulfate in the
29 diamond squid, *Thysanoteuthis rhombus*. *Bioscience, biotechnology, and biochemistry*
30 73(6), 1387-1391.

31 Tan, G.-K., Tabata, Y., 2014. Chondroitin-6-sulfate attenuates inflammatory responses
32 in murine macrophages via suppression of NF- κ B nuclear translocation. *Acta*
33 *biomaterialia* 10(6), 2684-2692.

34 TAT, S.K., PELLETIER, J.-P., MINEAU, F., DUVAL, N., MARTEL-PELLETIER, J.,
35 2010. Variable Effects of 3 Different Chondroitin Sulfate Compounds on Human
36 Osteoarthritic Cartilage/Chondrocytes: Relevance of Purity and Production Process. *The*
37 *Journal of rheumatology* 37(3), 656-664.

38 Thiele, H., Sakano, M., Kitagawa, H., Sugahara, K., Rajab, A., Höhne, W., Ritter, H.,
39 Leschik, G., Nürnberg, P., Mundlos, S., 2004. Loss of chondroitin 6-O-sulfotransferase-
40 1 function results in severe human chondrodysplasia with progressive spinal
41 involvement. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of*
42 *America* 101(27), 10155-10160.

43 Thomas, F., Jamin, E., Shimoo, K., Nagao, J., Osaki, Y., Granier, C., 2011. The use of
44 multi-element stable isotope analysis to monitor the origin of chondroitin sulfates.
45 *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry* 25(17), 2533-2537.

46 Thomson, D., Panagos, C.G., Venkatasamy, R., Moss, C., Robinson, J., Bavington,
47 C.D., Hogwood, J., Mulloy, B., Uhrin, D., Spina, D., Page, C.P., 2016. Structural
48 characterization and anti-inflammatory activity of two novel polysaccharides from the
49 sea squirt, *Ascidella aspersa*. *Pulmonary Pharmacology & Therapeutics* 40, 69-79.

1 Tuysuz, B., Mizumoto, S., Sugahara, K., Celebi, A., Mundlos, S., Turkmen, S., 2009.
2 Omani - type spondyloepiphyseal dysplasia with cardiac involvement caused by a
3 missense mutation in CHST3. *Clinical genetics* 75(4), 375-383.
4 Uygun, B.E., Stojisih, S.E., Matthew, H.W., 2009. Effects of immobilized
5 glycosaminoglycans on the proliferation and differentiation of mesenchymal stem cells.
6 *Tissue Engineering Part A* 15(11), 3499-3512.
7 Vázquez, J.A., Montemayor, M.I., Fraguas, J., Murado, M.A., 2009. High production of
8 hyaluronic and lactic acids by *Streptococcus zooepidemicus* in fed-batch culture using
9 commercial and marine peptones from fishing by-products. *Biochemical Engineering*
10 *Journal* 44(2-3), 125-130.
11 Vázquez, J.A., Montemayor, M.I., Fraguas, J., Murado, M.A., 2010. Hyaluronic acid
12 production by *Streptococcus zooepidemicus* in marine by-products media from mussel
13 processing wastewaters and tuna peptone viscera. *Microbial Cell Factories* 9(1), 46.
14 Vázquez, J.A., Pastrana, L., Piñeiro, C., Teixeira, J.A., Pérez-Martín, R.I., Amado, I.R.,
15 2015. Production of hyaluronic acid by *Streptococcus zooepidemicus* on protein
16 substrates obtained from *Scyliorhinus canicula* discards. *Marine Drugs* 13(10), 6537-
17 6549.
18 Vo, T.-S., Ngo, D.-H., Ta, Q.V., Kim, S.-K., 2011. Marine organisms as a therapeutic
19 source against herpes simplex virus infection. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical*
20 *Sciences* 44(1-2), 11-20.
21 Volpi, N., 1999. Disaccharide analysis and molecular mass determination to microgram
22 level of single sulfated glycosaminoglycan species in mixtures following agarose-gel
23 electrophoresis. *Analytical biochemistry* 273(2), 229-239.
24 Volpi, N., 2000. Hyaluronic acid and chondroitin sulfate unsaturated disaccharides
25 analysis by high-performance liquid chromatography and fluorimetric detection with
26 dansylhydrazine. *Analytical biochemistry* 277(1), 19-24.
27 Volpi, N., 2004. Disaccharide mapping of chondroitin sulfate of different origins by
28 high-performance capillary electrophoresis and high-performance liquid
29 chromatography. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 55(3), 273-281.
30 Volpi, N., 2007. Analytical aspects of pharmaceutical grade chondroitin sulfates.
31 *Journal of pharmaceutical sciences* 96(12), 3168-3180.
32 Watanabe, H., Yamada, Y., Kimata, K., 1998. Roles of Aggrecan, a Large Chondroitin
33 Sulfate Proteoglycan, in Cartilage Structure and Function. *The Journal of Biochemistry*
34 124(4), 687-693.
35 Wei, Y., Hu, Y., Hao, W., Han, Y., Meng, G., Zhang, D., Wu, Z., Wang, H., 2008. A
36 novel injectable scaffold for cartilage tissue engineering using adipose - derived adult
37 stem cells. *Journal of Orthopaedic Research* 26(1), 27-33.
38 Willis, C.M., Klüppel, M., 2014. Chondroitin Sulfate-E Is a Negative Regulator of a
39 Pro-Tumorigenic Wnt/Beta-Catenin-Collagen 1 Axis in Breast Cancer Cells. *PLoS*
40 *ONE* 9(8), e103966.
41 Wu, M., Huang, R., Wen, D., Gao, N., He, J., Li, Z., Zhao, J., 2012. Structure and effect
42 of sulfated fucose branches on anticoagulant activity of the fucosylated chondroitin
43 sulfate from sea cucumber *Thelecnata ananas*. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 87(1), 862-868.
44 Wu, M., Wen, D., Gao, N., Xiao, C., Yang, L., Xu, L., Lian, W., Peng, W., Jiang, J.,
45 Zhao, J., 2015. Anticoagulant and antithrombotic evaluation of native fucosylated
46 chondroitin sulfates and their derivatives as selective inhibitors of intrinsic factor Xase.
47 *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 92, 257-269.
48 Xu, H., Yan, Y., Li, S., 2011. PDLLA/chondroitin sulfate/chitosan/NGF conduits for
49 peripheral nerve regeneration. *Biomaterials* 32(20), 4506-4516.

1 Yamada, S., Sugahara, K., 2008. Potential Therapeutic Application of Chondroitin
2 Sulfate/Dermatan Sulfate. *Current Drug Discovery Technologies* 5(4), 289-301.
3 Yamada, S., Sugahara, K., Özbek, S., 2011. Evolution of glycosaminoglycans:
4 Comparative biochemical study. *Communicative & integrative biology* 4(2), 150-158.
5 Yue, Z., Wang, A., Zhu, Z., Tao, L., Li, Y., Zhou, L., Chen, W., Lu, Y., 2015.
6 Holothurian glycosaminoglycan inhibits metastasis via inhibition of P-selectin in
7 B16F10 melanoma cells. *Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry* 410(1), 143-154.
8 Zang, H., Li, L., Wang, F., Yi, Q., Dong, Q., Sun, C., Wang, J., 2012. A method for
9 identifying the origin of chondroitin sulfate with near infrared spectroscopy. *Journal of*
10 *Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis* 61, 224-229.
11 Zhang, W., Lu, Y., Xu, B., Wu, J., Zhang, L., Gao, M., Zheng, S., Wang, A., Zhang, C.,
12 Chen, L., 2009. Acidic mucopolysaccharide from *Holothuria leucospilota* has antitumor
13 effect by inhibiting angiogenesis and tumor cell invasion in vivo and in vitro. *Cancer*
14 *biology & therapy* 8(15), 1489-1499.
15 Zhang, Y., Kariya, Y., Conrad, A.H., Tasheva, E.S., Conrad, G.W., 2005. Analysis of
16 Keratan Sulfate Oligosaccharides by Electrospray Ionization Tandem Mass
17 Spectrometry. *Analytical Chemistry* 77(3), 902-910.
18 Zhao, L., Lai, S., Huang, R., Wu, M., Gao, N., Xu, L., Qin, H., Peng, W., Zhao, J.,
19 2013. Structure and anticoagulant activity of fucosylated glycosaminoglycan degraded
20 by deaminative cleavage. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 98(2), 1514-1523.
21 Zhao, L., Wu, M., Xiao, C., Yang, L., Zhou, L., Gao, N., Li, Z., Chen, J., Chen, J., Liu,
22 J., 2015. Discovery of an intrinsic tenase complex inhibitor: Pure nonasaccharide from
23 fucosylated glycosaminoglycan. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*
24 112(27), 8284-8289.
25 Zhao, Y., Nakajima, T., Yang, J.J., Kurokawa, T., Liu, J., Lu, J., Mizumoto, S.,
26 Sugahara, K., Kitamura, N., Yasuda, K., Daniels, A.U.D., Gong, J.P., 2014.
27 Proteoglycans and Glycosaminoglycans Improve Toughness of Biocompatible Double
28 Network Hydrogels. *Advanced Materials* 26(3), 436-442.
29 Zhao, Y., Zhang, D., Wang, S., Tao, L., Wang, A., Chen, W., Zhu, Z., Zheng, S., Gao,
30 X., Lu, Y., 2013. Holothurian Glycosaminoglycan Inhibits Metastasis and Thrombosis
31 via Targeting of Nuclear Factor- κ B/Tissue Factor/Factor Xa Pathway in Melanoma
32 B16F10 Cells. *PLoS ONE* 8(2), e56557.
33
34

Figure 1. Monosaccharides in GAGs

Figure
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 2. Chondroitin sulfate (CS) and dermatan sulfate (DS) disaccharide units. CS units consist of 4-linked D-glucuronic acid bound by alpha (1-3) glycosidic bond to D-galactosamine. In DS, D-glucuronic acid is epimerized to L-iduronic acid.

Figure
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 3. Biosynthesis of heparin/ heparan sulfate. An initial non-sulfated heparan polysaccharide is assembled by 1-4 alternate addition of glucuronic acid and acetylglucosamine. Subsequent incomplete reactions of sulfation, deacetylation and epimerization of the uronic ring lead to vast diversity in heparin/heparan sulfate chains.